

Synthetic methanol for shipping decarbonisation

STAKEHOLDER DECARBONIZATION STRATEGIES AND CHALLENGES

Deliverable D2.3

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable summarises the results of Task 2.2, which focused on the decarbonisation of the maritime sector and the challenges and opportunities of implementing alternative fuels such as e-methanol. The task explored the technical, environmental and regulatory aspects of maritime decarbonisation, highlighting key solutions such as carbon capture, energy efficiency and alternative fuels, with particular emphasis on e-methanol. A survey was distributed to interested stakeholders (Project partners and COP members), revealing their perspectives on the challenges, opportunities and roles they play in the decarbonisation process and the alternative fuels value chain.

Stakeholders identified significant opportunities and challenges in the adoption of alternative fuels such as e-methanol, hydrogen and e-ammonia. Although these fuels offer long-term benefits in terms of sustainability and regulatory alignment, the transition entails high initial costs, retrofit requirements and operational complexity. For shipowners, the switch to alternative fuels requires investment in vessels, equipment and crew training. Ports play a crucial role by investing in infrastructure to support the storage, handling and distribution of fuel.

Despite high production costs, e-methanol is considered a promising solution for decarbonisation of shipments, with efforts needed to reduce costs, scale infrastructure and ensure a stable supply chain. Policies and incentives will be key to encourage investment and reduce risks. Overall, the maritime sector recognises the need for sustainable technologies and is committed to overcoming financial and technical challenges to achieve long-term decarbonisation targets.

The document features 3 main chapters:

- **Chapter 2 - Decarbonisation of the maritime sector:** description of context, GHG emission related to maritime sector, by ship and fuel type; identification of regulatory framework and decarbonisation roadmaps; description of the main decarbonisation solutions and best-practices;
- **Chapter 3 - Alternative Fuels as Decarbonisation Solution:** the main alternative fuels (liquid biofuels, renewable gas fuels, hydrogen, methanol and ammonia) were analysed, indicating good practices, gaps in the implementation and readiness level and including safety issues;
- **Chapter 4 - Stakeholder decarbonisation strategies and challenges:** questionnaire structure description and main results; decarbonisation objective impacts on stakeholders; their role within the value chain aiming to reach decarbonisation goals.

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TABLE OF CONTENT

CHANGE CONTROL.....	2
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	3
TABLE OF CONTENT	4
LIST OF TABLES	5
LIST OF FIGURES.....	5
LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS	7
1 INTRODUCTION	9
2 DECARBONIZATION OF THE MARITIME SECTOR	10
2.1 EMISSIONS RELATED TO MARITIME SECTOR	10
2.2 EMISSIONS BY SHIP AND FUEL TYPE	13
2.3 REGULATORY FRAMEWORK AND DECARBONIZATION ROADMAP	16
2.3.1 IMO Regulations	18
2.3.2 Main EU Directives and Regulations	19
2.3.2.1 EU Directive 2023/959 - ETS	19
2.3.2.2 Fuel EU Maritime Regulation	20
2.3.3 Considerations on regulations	20
2.3.4 Future perspective and policy recommendations	22
2.4 DECARBONISATION SOLUTIONS.....	24
2.4.1 onboard Carbon Capture	24
2.4.1.1 Carbon Capture before combustion	25
2.4.1.2 Carbon Capture after combustion	26
2.4.2 Energy Efficiency measures and other reduction technologies.....	26
2.4.2.1 Changes in ship operations.....	28
3 ALTERNATIVE FUELS AS DECARBONISATION SOLUTION	31
3.1 ALTERNATIVE FUELS AND THEIR DECARBONISATION PATHWAY	31
3.1.1 Readiness of alternative fuel production pathways	36
3.1.2 Readiness of alternative fuel propulsion technologies	39
3.2 TECHNICAL ASPECTS AND INFRASTRUCTURE IMPLEMENTATION LEVEL	40
3.2.1 Liquid Biofuels	41
3.2.2 Renewable Gaseous Fuels.....	42
3.2.3 Hydrogen	42
3.2.4 Methanol	43

3.2.5	Ammonia.....	44
4	STAKEHOLDER DECARBONISATION STRATEGIES AND CHALLENGES	45
4.1	QUESTIONNAIRE STRUCTURE AND MAIN RESULTS	45
4.2	DECARBONISATION OBJECTIVES IMPACTS ON STAKEHOLDERS' ACTIVITIES	52
4.3	STAKEHOLDER'S ROLE WITHIN THE VALUE CHAIN AIMING TO DECARBONISATION	55
5	CONCLUSIONS	57
6	BIBLIOGRAPHY	58
	ANNEX A - SHIP TYPE DEFINITION.....	59
	ANNEX B - QUESTIONNAIRE STRUCTURE	61

LIST OF TABLES

TABLE 2.1: TOTAL SHIPPING CO ₂ EMISSIONS 2012-2018 (MILLION TONNES) – (SOURCE: IMO)	12
TABLE 2.2: POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS (SOURCE: UNCTAD)	22
TABLE 2.3: OVERVIEW OF OPERATIONAL SOLUTIONS (SOURCE: IRENA)	29
TABLE 2.4: OVERVIEW OF DESIGN SOLUTIONS (SOURCE: IRENA)	29
TABLE 3.1: SCREENING OF READINESS OF DISTRIBUTION, STORAGE AND BUNKERING INFRASTRUCTURES (SOURCE: IMO)	41
TABLE 4.1: MAIN CHALLENGES FACED IN IMPLEMENTING DECARBONISATION ACTIVITIES	47
TABLE 4.2: MAIN SAFETY AND ENVIRONMENTAL RISKS OF USING THE MAIN ALTERNATIVE FUELS	49
TABLE 4.3: DECARBONIZATION OBJECTIVE IMPACTS ON STAKEHOLDERS' ACTIVITIES	53

LIST OF FIGURES

FIGURE 2.1: EU'S GHG EMISSIONS IN 2019 BY TRANSPORT SUBSECTOR, INCLUDING DOMESTIC AND INTERNATIONAL COMPONENTS. (SOURCE: EEA)	10
FIGURE 2.2: GHG EMISSIONS FROM TRANSPORT IN EUROPE FROM 1990 TO 2024, WITH PROJECTIONS FROM 2024 TO 2040 (SOURCE: EEA)	11
FIGURE 2.3: GHG EMISSIONS FROM TRANSPORT IN EUROPE FROM 1990 TO 2040, BY TRANSPORT MODE AND SCENARIO (SOURCE: EEA)	12
FIGURE 2.4: WELL-TO-WAKE: HISTORICAL SHIPPING OPERATIONAL EMISSIONS AND FORECASTS (SOURCE: T&E)	13
FIGURE 2.5: TOTAL CO ₂ EMISSIONS BY VESSEL TYPES, TONS (SOURCE: UNCTAD)	14
FIGURE 2.6: INTERNATIONAL HFO-EQUIVALENT FUEL CONSUMPTION PER SHIP TYPE (SOURCE: IMO)	14
FIGURE 2.7: INTERNATIONAL, VOYAGE-BASED ALLOCATION, HFO-EQUIVALENT FUEL CONSUMPTION (THOUSAND TONNES), 2018, SPLIT BY MAIN ENGINE, AUXILIARY ENGINE AND BOILER. (SOURCE: UMAS/IMO)	15
FIGURE 2.8: GHG EMISSION BREAKDOWN ACROSS DIFFERENT PHASES OF OPERATION FOR EACH SHIP TYPE (SOURCE: IMO)	16
FIGURE 2.9: TIMELINE OF CANDIDATE SHORT-, MID- AND LONG-TERM GHG REDUCTION MEASURES (SOURCE: ABS)	17
FIGURE 2.10: 2023 IMO STRATEGY ON REDUCTION OF GHG EMISSIONS FROM SHIPS	17

FIGURE 2.11: IMO REGULATION DRIVES INNOVATION TO REDUCE THE CARBON INTENSITY OF INTERNATIONAL SHIPPING	18
FIGURE 2.12: READINESS OF ONBOARD CARBON CAPTURE TECHNOLOGIES (SOURCE: IMO)	24
FIGURE 2.13: RISKS RELATED TO CC ON BOARD (SOURCE: RINA)	25
FIGURE 2.14: FORECAST OF READINESS AND AVAILABILITY OF SELECTED ENERGY EFFICIENCY AND REDUCTION TECHNOLOGIES (SOURCE: IMO)	27
FIGURE 3.1: SUMMARY OF KEY ALTERNATIVE FUEL PATHWAYS FOR THE SHIPPING INDUSTRY (SOURCE: MMMCZCS)	32
FIGURE 3.2: ALTERNATIVE FUEL UPTAKE, WORLD ACTIVE FLEET AND ORDER BOOK, NUMBER OF VESSELS, 2022 (SOURCE: UNCTAD)	33
FIGURE 3.3: TRENDS IN ALTERNATIVE FUELS CAPABLE AND ENERGY SAVING TECHNOLOGY FITTED FLEET (EXPRESSED IN % OF ORDER BOOK AND GROSS TONS) – (SOURCE: UNCTAD)	34
FIGURE 3.4: 1.5 °C SCENARIO ENERGY PATHWAY, 2018-2050 (SOURCE: IRENA)	35
FIGURE 3.5: FEEDSTOCK REQUIREMENTS AND RANGE OF RENEWABLE ENERGY DEPLOYMENT ASSOCIATED WITH THE INCLUSION OF POWER FUELS IN THE 1.5 °C SCENARIO BY 2050 (SOURCE: IRENA)	36
FIGURE 3.6: FORECAST OF READINESS AND AVAILABILITY OF FUEL PRODUCTION PATHWAYS (SOURCE: IMO)	37
FIGURE 3.7: READINESS LEVEL OF SHIPPING FUELS (SOURCE: IRENA)	38
FIGURE 3.8: FORECAST OF READINESS AND AVAILABILITY OF CANDIDATE FUEL MARINE COMBUSTION ENGINE TECHNOLOGIES (SOURCE: IMO)	39
FIGURE 3.9: FORECAST OF READINESS AND AVAILABILITY OF MARINE FUEL CELL TECHNOLOGIES (SOURCE: IMO)	40
FIGURE 4.1: TYPE OF STAKEHOLDERS INVOLVED	45
FIGURE 4.2: BREAKDOWN OF KEY ACTIVITIES CARRIED OUT BY STAKEHOLDERS TO SUPPORT SHIPPING DECARBONIZATION	46
FIGURE 4.3: MAIN BARRIERS AND TECHNICAL CHALLENGES IN ADOPTING ALTERNATIVE FUELS FOR VESSELS	48
FIGURE 4.4: KEY ACTIONS TO SUPPORT THE ADOPTION OF ALTERNATIVE FUELS FOR DECARBONIZATION IN THE MARITIME SECTOR	52

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Description
ATR	Autothermal Reforming
BECCS	Bioenergy with carbon capture and storage
BECCUS	Bioenergy with carbon capture and storage or utilization
CBG	Compressed Biogas
CNG	Compressed Natural Gas
COP26	Clydebank Declaration of the Conference of the Parties 26
CII	Carbon Intensity Indicator
D	Deliverable
DAC	Direct air capture
EC	European Commission
EEA	European Economic Area
EEXI	Energy Efficiency Existing Ship Index
EU	European Union
FAME	Fatty Acid Methyl Esters
GHG	Greenhouse Gases
GT	Gross Tonnage
H ₂	Hydrogen
HFO	Heavy Fuel Oil
HVO	Hydrotreated Vegetable Oil
ILUC	Indirect Land-Use Change
JIT	Just-in-time
LBG	Liquified Biogas
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LNG	Liquefied Natural Gas
LOHC	Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carrier
LPG	Liquefied Petroleum Gas
ICCT	The International Council on Clean Transportation

ICE	Internal Combustion Engine
IMO	International Maritime Organization
MBM	Market Based Measure
MCFC	Molten Carbonate Fuel Cells
MEPC	Marine Environment Protection Committee
MMMCZCS	Mærsk Mc-Kinney Møller Center for Zero Carbon Shipping
NG	Natural Gas
OPS	Onshore Power Supply
RFNBO	Renewable Fuels of Non-Biological Origin
SEEMP	Ship Energy Efficiency Management Plan
SMR	Steam Methane Reforming
TRL	Technological Readiness
UMAS	University Maritime Advisory Services
UNCTAD	United Nations Conference on Trade and Development
WP	Work Package

1 INTRODUCTION

According to the Review of Maritime Transport 2023¹, while logistics, digitalisation, hydrodynamics, machinery, and "after treatment/carbon capture and storage" measures have the potential to reduce GHG emissions from shipping by an average of up to 30%, the greatest potential for significant GHG emission reductions lies in switching to low- or zero-carbon fuels. Shipping must replace fossil fuels with alternatives that do not emit GHGs throughout their entire life cycle (well-to-wake). Currently, there is no universally applicable solution available. The decarbonisation pathway indicates that zero-emission fuels need to constitute 5% of the international shipping fuel mix by 2030. The 2023 IMO GHG Strategy also commits to ensuring the adoption of alternative zero and near-zero GHG fuels by 2030, the Strategy aims for zero or near-zero GHG emission technologies, fuels, and/or energy sources to account for at least 5%, with an ambition of reaching 10% of the energy used by international shipping by 2030. While Fuel EU Maritime Regulation supports to reach the goal of reducing GHG emissions by at least 55% compared to 1990 levels by 2030.

This deliverable summarises the work done in the frame of Task 2.2 on "Decarbonization of the maritime sector, targets and challenges for the stakeholders; barriers and opportunities for the implementation of e-methanol in vessels". The objective of this task is to gather technical, environmental and regulatory aspects of the maritime sector decarbonisation, with a special focus on the use of alternative fuels for vessels' propulsion.

In the first instance, the general context was analysed, related to the decarbonisation of the maritime sector, mentioning briefly the emissions currently attributed to the maritime sector with focus on the type of ship and fuel used. After that, the regulatory framework and decarbonisation roadmaps proposed by IMO and EU, the related objectives and scenarios - including also future perspective and recommendations from UNCTAD - were described, focusing also to the decarbonisation solutions. Based on this context, the main decarbonisation solutions have been listed, including carbon capture, energy efficiency solutions and the adoption of alternative fuels. To better support the use case scenarios assessment, which will be further developed during WP5, the main alternative fuels (liquid biofuels, renewable gas fuels, hydrogen, methanol and ammonia) were analysed, indicating good practices, gaps in the implementation and readiness level and including safety issues.

Finally, a questionnaire with targeted questions has been distributed to the main stakeholders involved in efforts to decarbonise the maritime sector. The responses offered a critical view of the challenges and opportunities that each stakeholder faces in maritime decarbonisation and alternative fuel development. In addition, the results helped to identify the role of each stakeholder in promoting decarbonisation roadmap and goals and their direct involvement in the alternative fuels value chain, with particular emphasis on e-methanol.

¹ <https://unctad.org/publication/review-maritime-transport-2023>

2 DECARBONIZATION OF THE MARITIME SECTOR

2.1 EMISSIONS RELATED TO MARITIME SECTOR

According to the International Council on Clean Transportation (ICCT)², EU is the third-largest emitter of Greenhouse Gases (GHG) and crucial for the 1.5°C Paris Agreement target. Since 1990, EU transport emissions have grown by 33%, while other sectors reduced emissions by 32%. In 2018, transport contributed 29% of the EU's total greenhouse gas emissions. Light-duty vehicles are the biggest emitters, followed by heavy-duty vehicles, marine navigation, and aviation. In Figure 2.1 is reported the Transport Emissions in EU breakdown for 2019, elaborate by European Environment Agency (EEA), where it is noted that Navigation accounts for the 4% of the total EU emissions with 0.4% of domestic navigation and 3.6% international.

Figure 2.1: EU's GHG emissions in 2019 by transport subsector, including domestic and international components. (Source: EEA)

Besides domestic transport, international aviation and international maritime sectors also contribute to transport-related emissions. As highlighted also by EEA in the report on "Sustainability of Europe's mobility systems"³ and as shown in Figure 2.12, the EU's domestic GHG transport emissions show a weak downward trend since 2005. The most significant drop occurred in 2020 due to effects of the Covid-19 pandemic.

² <https://theicct.org/transport-could-burn-up-the-eus-entire-carbon-budget/>

³ <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/analysis/publications/sustainability-of-europes-mobility-systems>

Figure 2.2: GHG emissions from transport in Europe from 1990 to 2024, with projections from 2024 to 2040 (Source: EEA)

Emissions rebounded again in 2021 and 2022, before preliminary estimates indicate a slight decrease of 0.8% in 2023. According to their national emission projections, Member States expect a general decrease in transport emissions over the next decades. These projections differentiate between the expected emission reductions from current policies and measures⁴, and the additional reductions that planned measures can generate.

As reported in Figure 2.3, by 2030, current policies and measures are projected to deliver GHG emissions from transport that remain 4% above 1990 levels. With additional measures, those emissions would be 8% below 1990 levels. Most planned policies and measures in the transport sector focus on promoting low-carbon fuels or zero-emission technologies, as well as encouraging a modal shift to public transport.

The greatest increases up to 2030 are projected for aviation and international maritime transport. This continues the trend in emissions from both activities, which have grown since 1990. With road transport emissions set to decline, aviation and maritime emissions are therefore expected to constitute a higher proportion of transport sector emissions in the coming years.

⁴ The 'with existing measures' (WEM) projections scenario reflects the impact of policies already adopted and implemented at the Union level, while the 'with additional measures' (WAM) scenario includes implemented and planned EU policies and national targets.

Figure 2.3: GHG emissions from transport in Europe from 1990 to 2040, by transport mode and scenario (Source: EEA)

As reported in *Fourth IMO GHG Study 2020*, CO₂ remains the dominant source of shipping’s climate impact when calculated on a GWP-100-year basis, accounting for 98%, or 91% if Black Carbon is included, of total international GHG emissions (in CO₂e).

As reported in Table 2.1, at global level, in 2018, shipping was responsible for nearly 3% of global CO₂ emissions and about 11% of life-cycle transportation CO₂ emissions in 2020. From 2012 to 2018, CO₂ emissions from shipping increased by 10%, while methane emissions surged by 145% due to the rising use of natural gas as marine fuel.

Table 2.1: Total shipping CO₂ emissions 2012-2018 (million tonnes) – (Source: IMO)

Year	Total shipping CO ₂	Total shipping as a percentage of global
2012	962	2.76%
2013	957	2.74%
2014	964	2.74%
2015	991	2.81%
2016	1,026	2.90%
2017	1,064	2.97%
2018	1,056	2.89%

Even though the absolute emissions have increased in recent years, the carbon dioxide intensity per unit of transport (expressed in cargo capacity per nautical mile or cargo transported per nautical mile) has decreased for almost all types of ships, accordingly to the traffic increasing.

For what concern the whole life-cycle of the fuels and the Well-to-Wake emissions⁵, T&E elaborated the historical operational emissions including also the forecasts for Business-As-Usual scenario, Green Deal scenario and EU targets⁶, the emission trends are represented below:

Figure 2.4: Well-to-wake: historical shipping operational emissions and forecasts (Source: T&E)

2.2 EMISSIONS BY SHIP AND FUEL TYPE

According to the latest UNCTAD study and as shown in Figure 2.5 in, between 2012 and 2023 three ship types remain the dominant source of international shipping’s GHG emissions, especially for CO₂: container shipping, dry and bulk carriers, and tankers. According to IMO, in combination with chemical tankers, general cargo ships and liquefied gas tankers, accounted for around 88% CO₂ emissions from international shipping, and around 98% of total transport work in cargo tonne-miles throughout the period under observation.

⁵ “Well-to-wake” refers to the entire process of fuel production, delivery and use onboard ships, and all emissions produced therein.

⁶ <https://www.transportenvironment.org/state-of-transport/ships>

Figure 2.5: Total CO₂ emissions by vessel types, tons (Source: UNCTAD)

Regarding the main fuel consumption, Figure 2.6 presents the estimated fuel consumption break down across ship types (the definitions of each ship type is reported in Annex A), for each year of the 2012-2018 period, expressed in Heavy Fuel Oil (HFO) equivalent. It is noted that in this IMO analysis ammonia is not included.

Figure 2.6: International HFO-equivalent fuel consumption per ship type (Source: IMO)

Heavy fuel oil (HFO) continues to be the primary fuel in international shipping, accounting for 79% of total fuel consumption by energy content in 2018, based on voyage-based allocation. However, there has been a notable shift in the fuel mix during the study period. The share of HFO consumption decreased by about 7% (an absolute reduction of 3%), while the consumption of marine diesel oil (MDO) and liquefied natural gas (LNG) increased by 6% and 0.9% (absolute increases of 51% and 26%, respectively). Additionally, methanol emerged as a significant fuel during this period, reaching approximately 130,000 tonnes of consumption on voyage-based international routes (160,000

tonnes in total) in 2018. In the end, based on data from the University Maritime Advisory Services (UMAS), IMO has elaborated the estimated fuel consumption across onboard machinery with broadly different end uses (main engines – propulsion, auxiliary engines – electrical power and boilers – heat), reported in the figure below.

It is noted that energy use for propulsion remains the main energy demand across all ship types. However, for certain ship types, such as cruise ships, refrigerated bulk carriers, and various fishing vessels—the total energy demand for propulsion is roughly equal to the combined demand for auxiliary and heating/cooling energy. In addition to the type of fuel and its primary use, the phases of activity of each ship can influence the operation of the engines and equipment, the relative efficiency and therefore the GHG emissions.

Figure 2.7: International, voyage-based allocation, HFO-equivalent fuel consumption (thousand tonnes), 2018, split by main engine, auxiliary engine and boiler. (Source: UMAS/IMO)

In fact, as reported by IMO in Figure 2.8, the share of GHG emissions that occur at sea during manoeuvring, anchorage, or while berthed varies depending on the ship type. Among the six ship types most significant to emissions inventories, chemical and oil tankers have the highest proportion of their total GHG emissions (over 20%) occurring at, or near, ports or terminals. Container ships, cruise ships, and oil tankers have the smallest share of their total GHG emissions from cruising, due to the significant time spent in slow cruising or in phases at, or near, ports. Conversely, liquefied gas tankers and other liquid tankers have the largest share of their GHG emissions associated with cruising.

Figure 2.8: GHG emission breakdown across different phases of operation for each ship type (Source: IMO)

2.3 REGULATORY FRAMEWORK AND DECARBONIZATION ROADMAP

IMO and the EU are developing their strategies and measures to effectively mitigate GHG emissions, these measures can be independently applied.

The IMO Strategy on Reduction of GHG Emissions from Ships (2023 IMO GHG Strategy), recently adopted by the Marine Environment Protection Committee (MEPC 80), sets ambitious goals for the shipping industry that can be summarised as follows and as reported in Figure 2.9 and Figure 2.10:

- Reduce CO₂ emissions per transport work, on average in international shipping, by at least 40% by 2030 compared to 2008;
- Reduce GHG emissions by at least 20%, aiming for 30%, by 2030 compared to 2008;
- Reduce GHG emissions by at least 70%, aiming for 80%, by 2040 compared to 2008;
- Achieve zero GHG emissions impact around 2050, taking into account individual national contexts;
- Adopt zero or near-zero GHG emission technologies, fuels, or energy sources representing at least 5%, aiming for 10% of energy used in international shipping by 2030.

Figure 2.9: Timeline of candidate Short-, Mid- and Long-Term GHG Reduction Measures (Source: ABS)

Figure 2.10: 2023 IMO Strategy on Reduction of GHG Emissions from Ships

In parallel, on July 9th, 2021, the European Commission adopted the European Climate Law, which sets two highly ambitious goals for the EU:

- Reduce GHG emissions by at least 55% compared to 1990 levels by 2030;
- Achieve climate neutrality, meaning a 90% reduction in GHG emissions from the transport sector by 2050.

To achieve their respective targets by 2030, both the IMO and the EU have proposed significant

legislative measures, that have already come into effect, such as the IMO's short-term measures, or will soon come into effect, such as the EU's new requirements. In the following sections the main Regulations and Directives are presented.

2.3.1 IMO REGULATIONS

In line with the pace of work set by the initial IMO Strategy, and to achieve its ambitions, the MEPC 76 adopted in June 2021 a short-term GHG reduction measure (2018-2023) via amendments to MARPOL Annex VI. The measure consists of combined mandatory technical and operational requirements which entered into force in November 2022 and is aimed at reducing the carbon intensity of international shipping in 2030 by at least 40%, compared to 2008 levels.

The new requirements to Annex VI of MARPOL, significantly impact both new and existing ships with regards to:

- the calculation and verification of the new Energy Efficiency Existing Ship Index (EEXI);
- strengthening the Ship Energy Efficiency Management Plan (SEEMP);
- an energy efficiency assessment mechanism linked to the new Carbon Intensity Indicator (CII).

Figure 2.11: IMO regulation drives innovation to reduce the carbon intensity of international shipping

As mentioned in the previous section, regarding mid and long-term measures (2023-2030 and beyond 2030) to achieve the 2050 target defined in the 2023 IMO GHG Strategy, these will include a combination of technical measures (goal-based marine fuel standards) and economic measures (MBMs - market-based measures).

For economic measures, it may be desirable to impose a direct tax on fossil fuels to reduce the "green premium", where this term refers to the additional cost of using cleaner technology compared to one with higher emissions, aimed at promoting the adoption of sustainable fuels, as discussed,

and proposed by the MEPC 80.

The collected funds could be used, for example, to incentivise first movers, promote R&D projects, and finance alternative fuel infrastructure.

2.3.2 MAIN EU DIRECTIVES AND REGULATIONS

The EU requirements have been incorporated into the so-called "Fit for 55 Package" a package of rules that cover all sectors of the EU economy, including maritime transport, and aimed at achieving the 2030 climate target of reducing GHG emissions by 55%. The most significant legislative proposals for shipping are:

- the revision of Directive 2003/87/EC establishing a system for greenhouse gas emission allowance trading (ETS Directive);
- the new FuelEU Maritime Regulation, aimed at incentivising the use of low or zero carbon emissions alternative fuels.

2.3.2.1 EU DIRECTIVE 2023/959 - ETS

Directive (EU) 2023/959, amending the ETS Directive, will be implemented by European Member States and by Iceland and Norway, which are part of the European Economic Area (EEA), and applies from January 1st, 2024, to emissions from ships, regardless of their flag, exceeding 5,000 gross tonnages (GT). From January 1st, 2027, it will also apply to offshore units exceeding 5,000 GT.

The regulation covers:

- 100% of GHG emissions in European/EEA ports and for voyages between European/EEA ports;
- 50% of GHG emissions for voyages arriving in European/EEA ports from non-European ports or vice versa.

Where GHG emissions include CO₂ emissions from January 1st, 2024, methane (CH₄), and nitrous oxide (N₂O) emissions will be included from January 1st, 2026.

According to the Directive, starting from 2025 onwards, every shipping company operating in Europe has to:

- Report aggregated and verified emission data for the previous year (by March 31st of each year);
- Surrender the following allowances (by September 30th of each year):
 - 40% of the reported aggregated verified emissions for 2024;
 - 70% of the reported aggregated verified emissions for 2025;
 - 100% of the reported aggregated verified emissions for 2026 and each subsequent year.
- Pay a penalty of EUR 100 for each tonne of emissions for which allowances have not been surrendered.

Payment of the penalties does not exempt the Company from surrendering the allowances. If a Company fails to comply with the ETS Directive for two consecutive years, its ships may be denied entry to European ports until the Company fulfils its obligations.

It is important to highlight that EU ETS operates as a market where allowances are purchased and their values fluctuate according to market behaviour.

2.3.2.2 FUEL EU MARITIME REGULATION

The FuelEU Maritime Regulation, which is likely to be implemented by the Member States of the EEA, applies to ships with a gross tonnage (GT) of 5,000 or more that transport passengers or goods for commercial purposes, regardless of their Flag. The regulation covers the following:

- 100% of the energy used in European/EEA ports and for voyages between European/EEA ports;
- 50% of the energy used for voyages arriving in European/EEA ports from non-European ports or vice versa, and for voyages to and from remote regions of the EU.

The Regulation requires that:

- Starting from 2025, an annual average GHG intensity index must be calculated for each ship, which must not exceed a target value that will decrease significantly over the years (from 2% in 2025 to 80% in 2050). The calculation of the GHG intensity index requires to divide the total emissions of CO₂, CH₄, and N₂O by the energy used by the ship during the reference year. If the GHG intensity index exceeds the target, the company must pay a penalty proportional to the cost of renewable and low-carbon emission fuels that the ship should have used to comply with the regulation.

However, the regulation allows for the borrowing or banking of a ship's compliance surplus between two reference periods and for the pooling of two or more ships, even from different Companies. Compliant ships (i.e., with a GHG intensity index below the target or with paid penalties) must have a FuelEU Document of Compliance on board.

It is important to note that the possibility of forming ship "pools" promotes the use of alternative fuels, particularly biomethane or other biofuels that, when used on a limited number of ships, can still meet the standard, or mitigate the impact on the entire fleet.

- Starting from 2030, container ships and passenger ships berthed in EU/EEA ports subject to the "Alternative Fuels Infrastructure Regulation" (currently under development) must connect to onshore power supply (OPS) systems and use them to meet all energy needs while at berth unless:
 - they stay at the quay for less than two hours;
 - they use zero-emission technology (definition still subject to working groups);
 - they cannot connect due to compatibility/unavailability of connection points;
 - they need to carry out maintenance/functional tests;
 - there are safety/emergency reasons.

If this requirement is not met, the company is required to pay a penalty calculated based on the hours spent in port and the total electricity demand of the ship while berthed.

2.3.3 CONSIDERATIONS ON REGULATIONS

The decarbonisation strategies of the IMO and the EU operate independently and are based on different methodologies. The IMO mandates compliance with the MARPOL Annex VI Convention for

ships, without which they cannot operate. Conversely, the EU enforces a "polluter pays" principle, requiring payment for CO₂ emissions and imposing penalties for non-compliant ships. This difference in approach makes it extremely difficult for both shipbuilders and shipowners to identify a ship platform that can meet the needs of both regulations. Therefore, it is urgently necessary to harmonise both regulations to have a single global objective that makes the performance index on which the ship platform should be developed unequivocal. The current dichotomy makes the decarbonisation process difficult and significantly slows it down due to the high level of uncertainty it generates.

It is important to recognise that European measures are regional, impacting only traffic to, from, and within Europe. These measures could lead to market distortions and reduced competitiveness for the European maritime sector and its related industries. Therefore, if an international agreement is reached at the IMO level on issues already regulated by the EU, European regulations should be revised to align with the international standards. This approach, supported by European institutions, would prevent duplication of obligations and reduce administrative burdens for ships operating in Europe.

It should be emphasised that the application of regional rules imposes a managerial burden on shipping companies and, more importantly, market distortion.

Furthermore, in both regulations (IMO and EU), there are many implementation aspects that are still unclear or that leave room for interpretation, preventing a clear understanding for both shipbuilders and operators.

It is also crucial to develop and prepare rules for the training and education of crews who will operate on ships powered by alternative fuels. Almost all alternative fuels, in order to be managed safely, require a much higher level of preparation and competence than current fossil-based fuels. The risk is to have technologies and alternative fuels available but not enough maritime personnel trained to handle them.

The uncertainties mentioned above are limiting the propensity to invest in research on new technologies. To avoid the risk of having different rules and regulations regarding the same "tools" used and recognised for the calculation and measurement of:

- LCA (Life Cycle Assessment);
- GHG saving calculation;
- Sustainability criteria;
- Certification systems.

Both IMO and European regulations should achieve the same objectives and use the same tools.

This would allow for a homogeneous and easily applicable regulatory framework. Otherwise, operability would be unnecessarily penalised.

Therefore, it is necessary for all aspects to be considered as soon as possible so that all stakeholders (shipowners, operators, fuel producers, ports, Recognised Organizations, verifiers, and Flag Administrations) have a clear understanding of how to comply with their obligations.

Moreover, as highlighted in several documents submitted to the MEPC, any technical and/or economic measure alone or as part of a basket of measures is ineffective in achieving decarbonisation goals unless the availability of future fuels, new technologies, engines at affordable prices, and onboard personnel trained for their safe use are guaranteed.

Finally, both at the regional and international levels, funds collected through economic measures

can be used, for example, to incentivise first movers, promote R&D projects, and finance infrastructure for alternative fuels.

2.3.4 FUTURE PERSPECTIVE AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

At the MEPC 80 meeting in July 2023, significant progress was made in clarifying the timeline for the maritime fuel transition. However, the exact mix of future low and zero-carbon fuels remains undecided. Rapid advancement in IMO targets and regulations is crucial to meet decarbonisation goals. Energy production and bunkering systems must soon adapt to future fuel demands. The uncertainty around adopting green technologies and alternative fuels, coupled with regulatory ambiguities, raises the risk of stranded assets. Nevertheless, as the experience with key candidate fuels grows, this uncertainty should diminish.

A major risk is that shipowners might delay investments in fleet renewal, alternative fuels, and green technologies, adopting a "wait and see" approach to minimise costs. Such delays could result in ship capacity bottlenecks, supply chain disruptions, and higher shipping costs due to the substantial investments required for low-carbon transitions.

Fuel costs significantly impact vessel operating expenses, and the switch to low or zero-GHG fuels will likely increase costs, which could be passed on to shippers and consumers through higher freight rates and surcharges. Understanding how these new costs will be integrated into shipping rates is essential.

Due to the cross-border nature of shipping, decarbonising international maritime transport demands a global perspective. Implementing IMO regulation without disproportionately raising costs, especially for vulnerable economies, will require technical and financial support. An economic measure under IMO could help fund this assistance.

The UNCTAD published in 2023 some policy recommendations to reach the GHG emission targets of IMO (Figure 2.9), where robust collaboration is required among all stakeholders. Some key priority actions, especially related to alternative fuel value-chain, are summarised in the following table:

Table 2.2: Policy Recommendations (Source: UNCTAD)

Key action	Recommendation
Facilitate the fuel transition and enable a level playing field	Develop regulations and targets for zero and near-zero GHG fuels in shipping, and encourage carriers to adopt related energy sources, vessels, practices, and technologies.
	Support R&D and deployment of sustainable shipping technologies, including fuel-efficient engines, renewable energy, and emission reduction methods. Stimulate the supply of zero and low-carbon fuels for international shipping.
	Prepare for shipping fleets that simultaneously run on more than one fuel type and promote optionality through dual-fuel and tri-fuel designs.
	Promote sustainable facilities at ports, clean energy marine hubs and green shipping corridors that are more geographically, vessel and commodity-inclusive.
	Ensure stakeholders in seaports collaborate widely across the port ecosystem with fuel suppliers to ensure a sufficient supply of alternative low and zero-GHG fuels and infrastructure for distribution.

Key action	Recommendation
	<p>Assess the readiness of the alternative fuels and vessel designs, the sustainability and scalability of potential solutions and their regulatory and safety maturity levels</p> <p>Governments, academia, and public- and private-sector organisations should analyse the upstream footprint of alternative fuel production for shipping, including the GHG life cycle of the different fuels, as well as their full potential and production limits (e.g., biofuels)</p> <p>Ensure that international rules enable a level playing field and promote measures to lower the cost or price gap between alternative and conventional marine fuels.</p> <p>Create certainty regarding the volume of low and zero-carbon fuels and energy that will be needed at different points in time, through technical measures such as a fuel standard.</p> <p>Consider economic measures such as a levy that acts as a price for carbon to support the energy transition and incentivise investment in alternative fuels and green technologies for ships</p>
<p>Monitor impacts of the energy transition and decarbonization in shipping on costs, trade, and economic output</p>	<p>Monitor alternative fuel prices to help generate data for assessing the economic implications of decarbonization efforts. This information can guide decision-making processes, inform regulatory efforts, and boost sustainable, fair, and transparent shipping practices.</p> <p>Establish an advisory mechanism to guide the setting of freight rates and fuel surcharges. Communicate and monitor trends in freight costs and fuel surcharges. The advisory mechanism should bring together shipping, trade and relevant stakeholders in the maritime supply chain, including government and regulatory bodies. It could, for example, set guidelines on how to determine low and zero carbon fuel prices, freight rates and surcharges. This will help ensure transparency, and an inclusive operational environment and enable a smooth decarbonisation process. International organisations such as UNCTAD and IMO could provide support in this regard.</p>
<p>Align the regulatory framework in shipping with internationally agreed goals</p>	<p>Targets for usage of low and zero-carbon fuels in the shipping industry are needed to ensure progress on global climate mitigation objectives set out in the Paris Agreement.</p> <p>The regulatory framework should also ensure an equitable transition. In this regard, economic measures such as a carbon levy can help make alternative fuels competitive vis-à-vis GHG-generating traditional fuels and alleviate the transition costs in many developing countries. Support fleet renewal and avoid a capacity crunch in shipping.</p> <p>National and international regulations should minimize uncertainty, which prevents shipowners' timely investment in a new and modern fleet that runs on low or zero-carbon fuels and which delays the introduction of onboard and onshore energy-saving and green technologies.</p>

2.4 DECARBONISATION SOLUTIONS

This section describes the main technological solutions used in the maritime sector including the technologies of carbon capture present on board; the energy efficiency measures to adopt onboard and the suggested changes during the ship operations to reduce and optimize energy consumptions.

2.4.1 ONBOARD CARBON CAPTURE

Carbon capture on board is the only technology capable of making conventional maritime fuels compatible with emissions reduction targets and could be one of the key transitional solutions in the coming years. Despite its maturity as a land-based technology, several challenges persist for its maritime (onboard) implementation. These include the space required for CO₂ capture and storage on ships, the increased energy demand associated with various technologies, the certification of the system, the management and "ownership" of CO₂ once it is discharged from ships, the need to of training the onboard technical crew, and the need for clear regulations defining the criteria and limits for the commercialisation of CO₂ delivered to land. Investments in onboard carbon capture are expected to rise in the next decade as carbon regulations become more stringent. As reported in *Study on the readiness and availability of low- and zero-carbon ship technology and marine fuels* (IMO) and explained in detail in the next sections, onboard carbon capture systems can be applied to the exhaust gas of an engine, or the reforming of fuel into hydrogen for a fuel cell; their readiness is forecast in Figure 2.12.

Figure 2.12: Readiness of onboard carbon capture technologies (Source: IMO)

According to what is mentioned in the same report, carbon capture technologies applied to exhaust gas are operating commercially today in land-based systems but are still in the research and development stage for onboard use. Demonstrations are expected later this decade and the first commercial operation (at the capture rates required) in the 2030s.

Development of similar technology for fuel reformers is forecast to be slower. In both cases, as described above, there are energy (fuel use) penalties, practical and space challenges of installing capture equipment onboard as well as the necessary CO₂ storage onboard, and a need for handling and storage at ports. This means that the barriers to uptake, once onboard carbon capture is demonstrated, will no longer be technical readiness, but rather dependent on other factors including policy requirements/incentives, and so a forecast of commercialisation is unclear.

In addition to what was analysed in the study, it is worth noting the additional costs of any chemical additives required for the process. In the figure below, a dedicated study conducted by RINA⁷ shows

⁷ <https://scresources.rina.org/media/From-Today-to-2050-Challenges-and-Opportunities-for-the-Maritime-Industry.pdf>

the Risks related to CC on board and the potential mitigations:

Subject	Risks	Potential mitigations
Capture Rate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Maximum onboard capture rate currently 82%, which is lower than onshore application - Validation of CO₂ capture rate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Further improvement of onboard capture rate - Accurate measurement and recording systems
Energy Consumption	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Capture, liquefaction and storage requires large amount of additional energy (up to +40%) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Optimization with fuel type auxiliaries (like LNG) - Reduction of power for the liquefier (cryogenic decompression?)
Ship Integration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High volume and weight of capture and storage systems leads to potential cargo loss - Adaptation of shore- to marine-based environment requires additional considerations - Pre-treatment is needed depending on fuel such as denitration, desulfurization, and particulates) - (especially SO₂) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Arrangement of engine casing and engine room incl. height of equipment (absorption tower and reclamation tower) - Motion and vibration countermeasures for equipment - Handling of amine solution, saltwater damage countermeasures - Exhaust gas pre-treatment technology
Operations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Additional systems requires onboard management, maintenance, safety and handling requirements - Availability and cost of amine solution 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Additional crew to manage system and safety guidelines - Determine how specialized the amine solution needs to be and associated impacts
Cost	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Full application can be too costly (CAPEX 25-70% of newbuild price) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Optimization of target capture rate as a countermeasure to satisfy CII by retrofitting, combination with fuel conversion or optimization based on base ship design - Cost reduction as part of technology development process
CO ₂ Utilization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Limited CO₂ handling infrastructure - No framework to get credit for CO₂ reduction and limited market value 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CO₂ handling with shore facilities - Inclusion into future regulatory framework, tax and credit schemes setup,

Low risk remains
Medium risk remains
High risk remains

Figure 2.13: Risks related to CC on board (Source: RINA)

In addition to these risks, there is a lack of applicable requirements for CO₂ capture systems regarding installation, testing, monitoring, and certification. Currently, Annex VI to MARPOL does not regulate this technology.

From the perspective of principles established for testing, monitoring, and certification, there may be similarities with scrubbers (exhaust gas cleaning systems for sulphur oxides), such as the quality of discharge water, documentation, monitoring, and certification, which could potentially be applied to CO₂ capture systems.

In the following two sections, a brief description of the Carbon Capture methodology before and after combustion is detailed.

2.4.1.1 CARBON CAPTURE BEFORE COMBUSTION

Among the solutions to reduce ship CO₂ emissions, there are also pre-combustion fuel treatment options. For instance, LNG can be combined with steam in a gas reformer to convert LNG molecules into hydrogen and CO₂. The hydrogen is then used to power internal combustion engines or fuel cells, while the CO₂ is captured directly from the reformer's output, simplifying the capture process compared to extracting CO₂ from engine exhaust gases. Although this process requires additional fuel consumption, the emissions are offset by the effective CO₂ capture. This technology allows for the onboard production of hydrogen in the necessary quantities, avoiding the significant challenges associated with hydrogen storage. The significant advantage is that the cryogenic temperature of LNG as a fuel can liquefy the CO₂ from the reformed gas stream, which can then be collected and stored in a dedicated tank. It can be delivered to shore for further use or storage, or on-board tanker ships as inert gas.

2.4.1.2 CARBON CAPTURE AFTER COMBUSTION

The separation and capture of CO₂ from exhaust gases are usually carried out using the following methodologies:

1. Chemical absorption;
2. Physical adsorption;
3. Membrane separation;
4. Cryogenic distillation and other cryogenic capture methods;
5. CO₂ concentration using electrochemical devices.

It is worth noting that the exhaust gas cleaning systems currently installed on board and used for sulphur oxide and particulate matter removal are not suitable for CO₂ capture. However, pre-treatment of exhaust gases, especially those from fuels such as HFO, VLSFO, and MGO, may be necessary to enable better operation or longer lifespan of CO₂ capture technology. In practice, post-combustion CO₂ capture technologies need to work on exhaust gases already cleaned of particulates and sulphur oxides, making the installation of a scrubber often a prerequisite for the optimal functioning of the technology. Another promising technology that involves a chemical and physical process of the CO₂ molecule is represented by molten carbonate fuel cells (MCFC). MCFCs are not only highly efficient in CO₂ capture but also generate additional electricity. Ship engine exhaust gases can be treated with these devices, capturing up to 90% of CO₂ and producing a CO₂-rich captured stream that can be easily separated through a specific purification step applied at a flow rate one order of magnitude lower than the original exhaust gases.

2.4.2 ENERGY EFFICIENCY MEASURES AND OTHER REDUCTION TECHNOLOGIES

According to IMO, the shipping industry has developed and applied energy efficiency technologies for many years, driven by the desire to reduce fuel costs, and more recently by regulatory measures (e.g. EEDI, EEXI, CII). Several vessel design technologies are already mature and applied to many new vessels, including weight reduction, optimising hull dimensions, bulbous bow, bow thruster tunnel optimisation, and ballast and trim optimisation.

There remains potential for a wider roll-out of these technologies and hence greater fleet fuel savings in the future. A range of vessel energy efficiency and reduction technologies are not yet mature, and the forecast readiness of a selection of these is shown in Figure 2.14.

Figure 2.14: Forecast of readiness and availability of selected energy efficiency and reduction technologies (Source: IMO)

The current and forecast readiness of these vessel-based technologies, in Figure 2.14, are:

- Friction-reducing **advanced hull coatings** are already applied in commercial operations and are expected to reach full maturity before 2030. **Air lubrication** also serves to reduce hull friction. Although used on some vessels commercially today, some limitations have meant it has not yet become established. Commercial development is expected to improve its effectiveness and competitiveness by the late 2020s, reaching full maturity by 2035. The main hydrodynamic improvements can be summarised as follows:
 - Propulsion Optimization: this involves optimising the propeller-rudder coupling, changing blade designs for a new operating point, modifying hubs, using counter-rotating propellers, and employing flow-conveying fins to improve the hydrodynamic performance of the ship. This technology is ready, has a moderate impact, and involves design and dry-docking costs;
 - Hull and Propeller Maintenance: this includes monitoring performance, cleaning through brushing, high-pressure hull cleaning, and sandblasting. The technology is ready, has a moderate impact, and may incur additional costs for dry-docking. Underwater cleaning is not authorised in all ports.
 - Air Lubrication Systems: these systems cover the hull's surface in contact with water with air bubbles to reduce frictional resistance. This technology is ready and has a moderate impact.
 - High-Performance Hull Paint: the use of high-performance paints containing biocides or silicones can reduce frictional resistance. This technology is ready and has a moderate impact.
 - Optimization of Hull Openings: minimising water flow resistance through hull openings. This technology is ready and has a low impact.
 - Lightweight Ship Design: using new materials to reduce the weight of ships. This technology is in progress, has a low impact, and is applicable only to certain types of ships (e.g., small fast passenger ships).
- **Advanced waste heat recovery** systems recover useful energy from low-grade waste engine (or high-temperature fuel cell) heat. Although relatively recently developed for maritime use, they are starting to be used in commercial operations, and are forecast to be fully mature in a decade;
- **Shore power**: one of the most effective technologies for reducing, even eliminating, emissions

of local pollutants, such as SO_x, PM (smog), and NO_x is the ability to power the ship with electricity from the shore when in port. This allows the ship's engines to be turned off. Additional benefits of this solution include the reduction of CO₂ emissions, especially if the shore-based energy is entirely or partially from renewable sources, and the reduction of noise pollution from ship machinery. Many ships are already equipped to be powered from shore, so it is important to invest in port logistics for this solution, which, as mentioned above, offers several environmental advantages.

Considering that, as defined by the FuelEU Maritime and, starting from 2030, container ships and passenger ships moored in EU/EEA ports, to which the "Alternative Fuels Infrastructure Regulation" (under development) will apply, must connect to shore power supply (OPS) facilities, the urgency of investing in suitable infrastructure appears more than necessary.

So, this solution is transitioning from commercial operation to commercial development for larger vessels, with international standards in place. However, its high capital costs have been difficult to justify without firm demand, with unclear financial benefit to vessel operators or ports. As discussed before, favorable policies are starting to be adopted so they could be widely used (i.e. full maturity) within a decade;

- **Solar panels**, a fully mature technology on land, have been demonstrated onboard and are expected to be developed commercially later this decade. However, their use is expected to be limited by practical constraints, so the extent of their possible commercialisation is unclear;
- Directly transforming renewable wind energy into propulsion skips several steps and associated energy losses, making it an area worth focusing on. **Flettner rotors** which are now in use provide wind assistance on several vessels operating commercially, with commercial development expected to accelerate into the 2030s. Towing kites and **rigid sails** have achieved pilot demonstrations, and commercial operation is expected by 2025. However, not all wind assistance technologies are suited to all vessel types, so until their practicality and effectiveness have been more widely demonstrated their commercialisation paths are unclear.

2.4.2.1 CHANGES IN SHIP OPERATIONS

The IMO study has also forecast the readiness of technologies that increase the **operational voyage efficiency** of vessels. **Slow steaming** of vessels during voyages is already a mature measure. **Advanced autopilots** also assist in voyage optimisation with more recent developments ready and expected to be fully mature in the next 5 years; these include just-in-time arrivals for optimising fuel use. **Autonomous shipping** is currently at a research and development stage for which adequate regulations are still needed and is yet to be proven in all operational and weather conditions. Fully autonomous international trading vessels are not expected to be ready for commercial development for at least 10 years and full maturity may not be reached until 2050.

To meet the standards of EE, mandated by the IMO's EEDI, in 2013, new ship designs are required to apply a variety of structural EE measures. Through the IMO, the push to decarbonise the shipping sector is constantly adapting to the changes in technologies over the years. Where operational EE measures are tracked utilising EEOI and SEEMP, EEDI directly targets the design phase of vessels through measures that affect the hull and superstructure of the ship, the propulsion and power systems, machinery technologies integration, and the use of alternative energy sources. IRENA has developed a summary of the main operational and design energy efficiency solutions, reported in the tables below.

Table 2.3: Overview of operational solutions (Source: IRENA)

ENERGY EFFICIENCY OPERATIONAL SOLUTIONS	VOYAGE PERFORMANCE MANAGEMENT
	Just-in-time arrival
	Just-in-time (JIT) refers to the method whereby a ship optimises and maintains a particular speed to arrive at a port or piloting station in a timeframe that guarantees a berth, throughway or servicing.
	Ship speed optimisation
	Optimising speed during a ship’s journey is another important EE measure in conserving fuel. This process applies to new and existing vessels and is relatively easy to implement.
	Weather routing
	Weather plays an important role in ship pathing, and planning a route based on the weather allows for a safe voyage and accurate time of arrival.
	Autopilot improvements
	To mitigate energy consumption, autopilot software can be used to make calculated decisions about rudder movement to optimise its utilisation.
	Trim, draft, and ballast optimisation
	The draft, ballast and trim of a vessel are instrumental in dictating fuel and energy consumption. The trim of the ship dictates the ability of the ship to maintain a maximum speed while keeping the shaft power constant, thus reducing energy and fuel usage.
	ENERGY MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS
	Reducing onboard power demand
	To increase vessels’ EE, the power demand of all onboard machinery and equipment must be reduced.
Fuel quality and consumption reporting	
Fuel consumption is directly linked to vessels’ energy demand. Therefore, all ships have a system of fuel consumption monitoring and reporting for bunkering logistics and fleet cost management. Improvements in monitoring these aspects can reduce vessels’ fuel consumption.	
VESSEL MAINTENANCE MEASURES	
Hull roughness management	
Hull roughness determines the amount of friction between the ship and the water. Too much frictional force on the ship increases energy demand and fuel consumption. To mitigate this, various methods can be applied to maintain optimum roughness of the hull.	
Propeller roughness management	
Propeller roughness is caused by corrosion and fouling from organisms such as those that affect hull roughness. Therefore, shipowners should maintain propellers by polishing and coating them.	

Table 2.4: Overview of design solutions (Source: IRENA)

ENERGY EFFICIENCY	HULL AND SUPERSTRUCTURE
	Ship sizing
	Larger capacity ships tend to be more energy efficient due to their ability to transport more cargo at

HULL AND SUPERSTRUCTURE		
DESIGN SOLUTIONS	the same speed as smaller vessels while expending less power.	
	Principal dimensions	
	Designs for new ships should optimise the length/beam ratio by increasing the length and decreasing the beam of the vessel while maintaining the draft.	
	Ship weight	
	The structural weight of a vessel impacts a ship's EE and fuel consumption performance. The benefits of a lighter structural weight are proportional to ship size, with larger ships seeing increased efficiencies and reduced fuel consumption.	
	Aft body and forebody optimisation	
	Designs integrated into the forebody of the vessel include the design of the bulb, waterline entrance, forward shoulder and bilge (ABS, 2013). Aft body optimisation mitigates stern waves, improves flow towards the propeller and avoids the eddy effect.	
	PROPULSION SYSTEMS	
	Propeller optimisation	
	Various forms of high-efficiency propellers exist. Each propeller installation is required to be designed specifically to suit a ship's operational profile and stern hydrodynamics.	
Enhancement of propulsion drives		
These are devices that provide wake equalisation and flow separation alleviation to improve the flow around the hull of a ship by mitigating issues arising from the propeller and hull resistance.		
Air lubrication systems		
Air lubrication systems can prove instrumental in mitigating resistances on a vessel, thus improving propulsion. Two forms of air lubrication exist: air cavity systems and micro-bubble systems.		
POWER SYSTEMS		
Main engines		
The use of main engine efficiency measurement instrumentation is a key EE measure to track a ship's fuel consumption and energy demand. This includes shaft power meters, fuel flow meters and engine performance measurement and control.		
Auxiliary equipment		
Improvements to a ship's auxiliary systems in the design stage can boost the vessel's EE. Hybrid auxiliary power generation systems consisting of fuel cells (FCs), diesel/gas generators and batteries can improve ship energy performance.		
Assisted propulsion by wind and solar		
Various measures can be integrated into a ship's design to assist propulsion, such as towing kites, which are common and commercially available (see Box 9). The introduction of solar power to vessels is also currently in development. In vessels, solar photovoltaic (PV) panels can be best used to power auxiliary systems and supplement a vessel's power demand.		

3 ALTERNATIVE FUELS AS DECARBONISATION SOLUTION

Alternative fuels, depending on the feedstock used and the specific production pathways involved, are often identified using colour codes. “Grey/black” and “brown” fuels are generated from fossil fuels. “Blue” fuels are sourced from fossil fuels, but carbon emitted during their production is captured and stored using carbon capture and storage from either direct air capture or point source. “Green” refers to fuels produced with electrolysis powered by renewable energy, also known as “e-fuels”. It is noted that green fuels also include fuels produced from biomass sources (also known as “biofuels”).

The following sections will describe the main alternative fuels for the maritime sector, examining future trends, best practices and key challenges associated with their production. This will include an assessment of the readiness to adopt each fuel, its advantages and disadvantages, as well as an analysis of safety aspects.

3.1 ALTERNATIVE FUELS AND THEIR DECARBONISATION PATHWAY

As mentioned in *A Pathway to Decarbonise The Shipping Sector by 2050*, published by IRENA in 2021 and reported in *Review of Maritime Transport 2023* published by the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD), alternative fuels, depending on the feedstock used and the specific production pathways involved, are often identified using colour codes. “Grey/black” and “brown” fuels are generated from fossil fuels. “Blue” fuels are sourced from fossil fuels, but carbon emitted during their production is captured and stored using carbon capture and storage. “Green” refers to fuels produced from biomass sources and (also known as “biofuels”) and to fuels produced with biogenic CO₂ and green/renewable hydrogen. In the following figure, published in 2024 by Mærsk Mc-Kinney Møller Center for Zero Carbon Shipping (MMMCZCS), a summary of key alternative fuel pathways for the shipping industry is reported:

Figure 3.1: Summary of key alternative fuel pathways for the shipping industry (Source:MMMCZCS)⁸

As declared by IRENA in 2021, the alternative energy fuels most suited for international shipping are primarily advanced biofuels and e-fuels (i.e., synthetic fuels), namely methanol and ammonia. Each alternative energy fuel varies in terms of benefits and challenges. The choice of fuel depends on factors such as the supply chain, engine technology, environmental impacts and production costs

Ammonia is more attractive as it has zero carbon content when produced from renewable sources. It does not require capturing CO₂ emissions, which can increase the final cost of e-methanol. But methanol is gaining attention while hydrogen, sail power, biofuels and other technologies are being explored, including batteries. Electric and hybrid propulsion systems relying on batteries or a combination of batteries and diesel or gas engines are also evolving, especially among small and coastal tonnage.

As reported in *Review of Maritime Transport 2023*, the transition to alternative fuels is still in its infancy. A total of 98.8% of the global fleet in terms of the number of vessels use conventional fuels. Only 1.2% are using alternative fuels, mainly liquefied natural gas (LNG), and to a lesser extent, battery/hybrid, liquefied petroleum gas (LPG), and methanol, as shown in **Error! Reference source not found.**

⁸ <https://www.zerocarbonshipping.com/publications/global-availability-of-biogenic-co2-and-implications-for-maritime-decarbonization/>

Figure 3.2: Alternative fuel uptake, world active fleet and order book, number of vessels, 2022 (Source: UNCTAD)

Progress is underway as 21% of vessels currently on order are designed to run on alternative fuels, notably LNG, LPG, battery/hybrid and methanol. While nearly 6% of the active fleet are operating on alternative fuels, mainly LNG. It should be noted that while LNG may have a lower carbon footprint than heavy fuel oils, it remains a fossil fuel and faces problems such as methane slip and ‘well-to-tank’ emissions. As for batteries, these are more suited for use by vessels operating on shorter distances.

It is important to highlight that technological readiness, scalability, and regulatory certainty are required to firm up demand for alternative fuels and vessels. Testing and demonstration, which allows for a solid proof of concept is important given the average age of the existing vessel feet and the long lifespan of ships (25 to 30 years). In this context, the design of new vessels and engines needs to occur now to enable the deployment of zero-carbon vessels fuelled by alternative fuels. These vessels will still be in operation in 2050 (IRENA, 2021).

As mentioned before, shipowners are facing the dilemma of whether to order additional capacity and renew their fleets now, despite the uncertainty surrounding the best alternative fuels and technologies, or to wait until the alternative fuel pathways and regulations become clearer. Fleet renewal requirements, concerns about shipbuilding yard capacity, and higher construction costs are creating challenges and complicating investment decisions for shipowners. The mid-term measure will not take effect until 2027, at the earliest. From that year onwards, a portion of the fleet will be able to utilise these alternative fuels and green technology options.

As illustrated in **Error! Reference source not found.**, alternative fuel capacity on order increased in recent years, particularly since the COVID-19 pandemic. At the same time, vessels fitted with energy-saving technologies and eco-ships with electronic engines also gained attraction in recent years.

Figure 3.3: Trends in alternative fuels capable and energy saving technology fitted fleet (expressed in % of order book and gross tons) – (Source: UNCTAD)

According to what was declared by DNV, one estimate suggests that achieving full decarbonisation by 2050 requires the fuel infrastructure to deliver around 270 million tons of the heavy fuel oil equivalents of alternative fuels. Switching to alternative fuels requires investments in the fuel infrastructure that will outpace onboard vessel investments. As the development of alternative low- or zero-carbon fuels is mainly in the hands of out-of-sector stakeholders (fuel producers and suppliers, engine manufacturers, shipyards etc.), collaboration across the wide-ranging stakeholders from inside and outside the shipping sector is crucial.

The updated IMO GHG strategy indicates that the bulk of the maritime sector’s energy transition needs to be completed by 2040. It is crucial to ensure that the necessary regulatory, technological, and safety standards are adequately developed and ready. Moreover, since ports and terminals encounter similar uncertainties and challenges as shipowners concerning future fuels and regulations, efforts should focus on accelerating the transition. This includes facilitating timely investments in port cargo handling equipment, infrastructure, storage facilities, and the replacement or construction of new terminals.

Regarding the specific type of fuels that will shape the shipping sector’s future energy demand, regulations imposing a carbon levy would greatly support a shift towards the use of renewable fuels, including green H₂-based fuels and biofuels. Fuel price and availability will also be decisive factors in the choice of renewable fuel/propulsion technology. Other key decisive factors will include the infrastructural adaptation costs of ships and ports, technological maturity and sustainability issues (e.g. food security). The willingness and ability of shipping companies to pay a premium price for low-carbon products will also be decisive (IRENA, 2019).

The overall transition from 2018 to 2050 from a carbon-intensive sector, currently predominantly based on the use of fuel oil and MGO, to a decarbonised sector in 2050 with a high inclusion of renewable fuels is illustrated in **Error! Reference source not found.**, showing the estimated ranges of solar and wind power required to meet the necessary levels for green H₂.

Figure 3.4: 1.5 °C Scenario energy pathway, 2018-2050 (Source: IRENA)

It is noted that IRENA scenarios explored the potential of these two renewable fuels in the international shipping sector and the role that each may have in the path to a decarbonised sector in 2050.

However, the IRENA 1.5°C scenario presents renewable ammonia as having a participation 4.5 times more significant than that of renewable methanol. Unlike ammonia, the utilisation of methanol requires little engine modifications, a clear advantage of this renewable fuel. However, the production of renewable methanol requires CO₂-free carbon as a feedstock. The costs linked to CO₂ as a feedstock result in a higher cost of e-methanol when compared to e-ammonia. However, if technology costs for Direct air capture (DAC) and Bioenergy with carbon capture and storage or utilization (BECCUS) fall significantly in the next decade, it could be possible that methanol rather than ammonia will become the fuel of choice.

In addition, considering the relevance that green H₂-based fuels are expected to have in the decarbonisation of the shipping sector, IRENA establishes the feedstock requirements (**Error! Reference source not found.**) and estimates renewable energy ranges that would be required to satisfy the demand for power fuels for the 1.5°C scenario by 2050. As indicated below, the overall requirement for green H₂ for 2050 stands at 46 Mt. Of this amount, 74% would be required to produce ammonia, 16% for methanol and the remaining 10% would be directly employed as green H₂. The figure below also presents the estimated ranges of solar and wind power that would be required to meet the required levels of green H₂. However, several factors will dictate the precise capacity of renewable energy to be deployed up to 2050. The renewable power technology of choice and average capacity factors associated with each renewable energy plant supporting the production of green H₂ will play a role in the final energy capacity. Accordingly, in the years to come it will be fundamental to choose the geographical locations with the most renewable energy resources to ensure cost-effective investments that subsequently result in a competitive cost for power fuels.

Note: The estimated solar PV capacity and wind capacity are mutually exclusive and cumulative.

Figure 3.5: Feedstock requirements and range of renewable energy deployment associated with the inclusion of power fuels in the 1.5 °C Scenario by 2050 (Source: IRENA)

3.1.1 READINESS OF ALTERNATIVE FUEL PRODUCTION PATHWAYS

According to the study about the readiness and availability of alternative fuels conducted by IMO and published in 2023⁹, decarbonisation will require low- and zero-carbon fuels like advanced biofuels, renewable e-fuels, and blue fuels with carbon capture. While these fuels could be widely available by 2030, their supply depends on demand, incentives, and supportive policies. Some fuels can use existing infrastructure, while others will need new facilities. The shipbuilding industry can scale up production if demand is clear, and the necessary technologies are ready for deployment. Although these fuels are more expensive than current options, they can be adopted if demand is strong, and costs are planned over time.

The above-mentioned study considered the following “candidates” as fuels:

- biofuels derived from biomass (algae, waste) such as biomethanol, biomethane, and biodiesel;
- synthetic fuels or non-biological renewable origin fuels (RFNBO subset of e-fuels) based on hydrogen produced by electrolysis using renewable or nuclear energy. This category includes carbon-free fuels such as synthetic hydrogen, synthetic ammonia, or direct carbon capture from biogenic sources, such as synthetic methanol, synthetic methane, or synthetic diesel;
- "blue fuels" based on hydrogen from fossil sources and carbon capture greater than 90%, such as blue hydrogen and blue ammonia;
- electricity from the grid, produced from both fossil and renewable sources and made available as shore power;
- fossil fuels blended with certified sustainable biofuels with onboard carbon capture greater than 70% (similarly for synthetic fuels).

In Figure 3.6 the forecast readiness of the fuel production pathways is reported, where it is noted

⁹ <https://wwwcdn.imo.org/localresources/en/MediaCentre/WhatsNew/Documents/MEPC80.INF10.pdf>

that biofuel and e-fuel pathways are advancing toward commercial maturity, with notable developments anticipated before 2030.

Figure 3.6: Forecast of readiness and availability of fuel production pathways (Source: IMO)

Biofuels include but are not limited to, biodiesel, which is in very high use in road transport and, in small quantities more recently, shipping. To further develop these biofuels, the next steps will involve the scaling up of production facilities and the waste feedstocks. This scaling-up process may be affected by competition over these feedstocks and may thereby influence their availability. Biomethane and biomethanol are also currently used. In the same way, their industrial production would require an increase in both the number of plants and feedstock produced, which may impose the consequence of a competitive situation where more demand would create competition for sources.

E-fuels, including green hydrogen and ammonia, will move on from demonstration into commercial operation with full maturity in the 2030s. Thus, investment in both production plants and renewable sources is crucial. Direct air capture of CO₂, expected to reach commercial availability around 2030, will also be key to scale up production. For e-methane, some pilot plants have been built, although their development has been less extensive than the development of e-methanol. E-methanol riding on the demand from the roads sector, are likely to attain commercial maturity only during the early 2030s. However, demand from the road sector could create competition for supply, but on the same time, the phase out of thermal engines for new cars in Europe would make available big amount of biodiesel and bio methanol that could become available for other purposes. On the road to blue fuels, blue hydrogen and ammonia are expected to reach complete maturity before 2030 and in the middle of the 2030s, respectively. The CCS technologies available today have their criticalities, especially with large-scale steam methane reforming while producing blue hydrogen. Development around autothermal reforming is bound to improve efficiencies in CCS. Full commercialisation of blue fuels will thus depend more on economic considerations than on purely technical issues. Retrofitting CCS in already operating plants can be limited, and permanent CO₂ storage should be reliable.

Overall, while advanced biofuels and blue fuels are getting closer to full commercial maturity, e-fuels are very much in transition, their prospects dependent upon further technological development in combination with investment.

In summary, each alternative fuel has advantages and disadvantages in terms of physical

characteristics, and therefore it is important to consider logistical, infrastructural and safety aspects when choosing an alternative fuel. The alternative fuels considered for the shipping industry include biofuel, biogas, methanol, ammonia, H₂ and FCs. Each of these fuel options has benefits and challenges, summarised in *A Pathway to Decarbonise The Shipping Sector by 2050*, published by IRENA in 2021 and shown in Figure 3.7.

4 Readiness level of shipping fuels (● High - ● Medium - ● Low)

	FUEL TECHNOLOGICAL READINESS	ENGINE TECHNOLOGICAL READINESS	SCALABILITY & TIME TO MARKET	ENERGY DENSITY	GHG REDUCTION	ENGINE TECHNOLOGY	ADVANTAGES	CHALLENGES
Fuel Oil	High	High	High	High	Low	ICE	Already used globally, has high efficiency and is low cost in comparison to alternative fuels.	HFO has high carbon emissions and particulate emissions from production and use in vessels.
LNG	High	High	Medium	High	Low	ICE	Well-established supply infrastructure, high energy density and is currently used in vessels globally. Has a lower sulphur content than HFO.	LNG has fewer emissions compared with HFO but still significantly more emissions than low-carbon alternative fuels. Uses non-renewable resources.
Advanced Liquid Biofuels	High	High	Low	High	Medium	ICE	Biofuels have an established infrastructure due to use in multiple sectors. Easy integration into current engines. Can be used as a drop-in fuel.	Growth of feedstock used in biofuel production may affect land use, which could impact global food security. High demand from multiple sectors makes scaling difficult.
Renewable Gaseous Fuels	High	High	Low	High	Medium	ICE	Bunkering in ports can use LNG infrastructure, making implementation cheaper. Ships that use LNG can switch to liquefied biogas (LBG) as a drop-in fuel.	Limitations with storage capacity required for LBG. Can only be considered for short-distance vessels. Long-distance vessels would require large storage capacity.
Hydrogen	Low	Low	Medium	Low	High	ICE FCs	Employing green H ₂ would lead to nearly zero carbon emissions. A main option as an energy carrier in FCs. Multiple applications across sectors, which can increase the rate of research.	H ₂ production and storage is costly, requiring cryogenic storage. Still an immature technology in the shipping sector but has high potential as an alternative fuel.
Ammonia	High	Low	Medium	High	High	ICE FCs	Ammonia has existing production and transport infrastructure due to the agricultural industry. Green ammonia is carbon neutral and has one of the highest efficiencies when compared to alternative fuels.	Global demand for ammonia across multiple sectors can cause scalability issues. Ammonia has a high production cost and is highly toxic, requiring special storage and safety measures.
Methanol	High	High	High	High	High	ICE FCs	Currently used in a multitude of sectors and can be implemented within the shipping sector with relative ease. Using e-methanol and bio-methanol is 100% renewable.	Difficulties in acquiring sustainable and cost-effective carbon sources. Green methanol has high production costs.

Figure 3.7: Readiness level of shipping fuels (Source: IRENA)

3.1.2 READINESS OF ALTERNATIVE FUEL PROPULSION TECHNOLOGIES

As reported in the IMO study, ships using conventional fuels have internal combustion engines to generate propulsion or electrical power; similar engines are possible for the candidate fuels. In addition, fuel cells are an emerging technology for the maritime industry, offering efficiency and other benefits. The readiness of both groups of technologies for use with the candidate fuels has been evaluated in the following figures. The potential for retrofitting existing vessels has also been considered in the study. Retrofitting a vessel with a fuel cell powertrain is more complex than converting an engine to using an alternative fuel, on top of the need to change fuel storage and supply systems. However, building new vessels with possible future conversions in mind – such as using an electric propulsion system (already established technology) – could make a switch from engines to fuel cells, a more practical proposition.

Figure 3.8: Forecast of readiness and availability of candidate fuel marine combustion engine technologies (Source: IMO)

Marine engines already use biodiesel blended with conventional fuels, and engines capable of using pure biodiesel are expected to mature by the late 2020s, as few technical barriers exist. Bio- and e-diesel are compatible with existing diesel engines with minimal modifications and can also serve as pilot fuels to initiate combustion of other fuels.

Methane engines, particularly those using LNG, are fully mature, with biomethane and e-methane easily substitutable without technical challenges. Methanol engines are already commercially viable, with increasing development, especially for 2-stroke engines, and are expected to reach full maturity before 2030. Retrofitting vessels to use methanol is a practical option for oil-fuelled ships, more so than converting to gas fuels.

Hydrogen 4-stroke engines are in the demonstration phase and should be commercially available later this decade, though regulations and storage requirements may limit their use to shorter voyages. Retrofitting for hydrogen is possible but complex due to storage and handling issues. Larger 2-stroke engines are not expected to adopt hydrogen due to these constraints.

Ammonia engines are in the research and development stage, with pilot demonstrations expected by 2025 and commercial operation before 2030. Commercialisation is expected to progress rapidly because the technology requires minimal changes from existing engines. Ammonia offers better energy storage density than hydrogen, though retrofitting may be challenging for oil-fuelled vessels but more feasible for LNG-fuelled ships.

Figure 3.9: Forecast of readiness and availability of marine fuel cell technologies (Source: IMO)

Hydrogen fuel cells are currently being piloted, with commercial operations anticipated in the late 2020s, particularly for smaller vessels. Key challenges include scaling up power output, ensuring reliability for sustained operations, fuel storage and handling, and regulatory development. Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carrier (LOHC) technology, which allows for higher-density hydrogen storage, is also expected to be commercialise within the same timeframe as hydrogen fuel cells.

Methane and methanol fuel cells are forecast to begin commercial operations around 2030, with full maturity expected to take a decade. These fuels can be used directly in some fuel cells or reformed onboard to produce hydrogen. Vessels using methane or methanol engines for propulsion could accelerate the adoption of these fuel cells by utilising them for auxiliary power.

Ammonia fuel cells are expected to be piloted in the late 2020s, but onboard cracking of ammonia into hydrogen may commercialise sooner. Cracking ammonia into hydrogen expands the range of compatible fuel cells, though it adds complexity. The full commercial adoption of ammonia fuel cells for propulsion remains uncertain, as it will depend on how they compare to ammonia engines in terms of efficiency, cost, and durability.

3.2 TECHNICAL ASPECTS AND INFRASTRUCTURE IMPLEMENTATION LEVEL

The growing demand for alternative fuel ships will increase the need for bunkering facilities. Several port and bunkering investment projects are anticipated, including green maritime corridors, which could play a key role in ensuring the availability of specific green fuels along designated routes through collaboration between ports and fuel producers. Biodiesel, e-diesel, and biomethane can use existing bunkering infrastructure, while ammonia and hydrogen will require new refuelling infrastructure to be built. To prevent limitations on the use of these fuels, assuming they are available, it is essential that bunkering infrastructure, distribution, and storage capacities are adequately developed. For methanol, which has a flashpoint below 60°C, adjustments to the current bunkering infrastructure may be necessary, though these adjustments will not involve cryogenic or high-pressure modifications. Ensuring that these fuels are available will depend on sufficiently developed bunkering and distribution systems to avoid potential constraints.

IMO has evaluated how well aligned the current distribution and storage and the bunkering infrastructure are for each group of candidate fuels, reported in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1: Screening of readiness of distribution, storage and bunkering infrastructures (Source: IMO)

Fuel types	Distribution and storage	Bunkering infrastructure
Fuel oils (e-diesel, biodiesel)	Can use existing distribution and storage facilities for distillate fuel	Can use existing bunkering infrastructure for distillate fuel
Gaseous fuels (e-methane, biomethane)	Can use existing (and still developing) distribution and storage facilities for LNG	Can use existing (and still developing) LNG infrastructure
Methanol (e-methanol, biomethanol)	Can build on existing storage and distribution infrastructure from global network of terminals, used for global methanol trading/transport	Demonstration bunkering operations have been successful, ship-to-ship bunkering proven. Partially developed bunkering infrastructure at 90 ports worldwide.
Ammonia (e-ammonia, blue ammonia)	Can build on existing storage and distribution infrastructure from global network of terminals, used for global ammonia trading/transport	No bunkering infrastructure today, and no bunkering operations demonstrated. Barriers remain to be solved.
Hydrogen (e-hydrogen, blue hydrogen)	No existing distribution infrastructure	No existing bunkering infrastructure Local bunkering operations have been demonstrated. Barriers remain to be solved.

The high-level screening is given for 3 readiness levels:

Green: Mature and proven; Amber: Solutions identified; and Red: Barriers remain.

In summary, bio- and e-diesel, and bio- and e-methane will be able to use existing bunkering infrastructure, while ammonia, hydrogen and methanol will need new bunkering infrastructure to be built. Infrastructure will need to be tailored to each fuel’s characteristics, with these ranges of characteristics posing a new complexity in infrastructure development.

As analysed by IRENA¹⁰, in the following sections, scalability, infrastructure implementation level and key concepts are discussed for each category of fuel.

3.2.1 LIQUID BIOFUELS

According to EU definition¹¹ liquid biofuels include all liquid fuels of natural origin (e.g. produced from biomass and/or the biodegradable fraction of waste), suitable to be blended with or replace liquid fuels from fossil origin. Infrastructure for this kind of fuels can leverage on existing HFO bunkering infrastructure. Biofuels for shipping will also have to compete for supplies against other industries depending on biofuels for decarbonisation.

The main liquid biofuels are Hydrotreated Vegetable Oil (HVO) and Fatty Acid Methyl Ester

¹⁰https://www.irena.org/-/media/Files/IRENA/Agency/Publication/2021/Oct/IRENA_Decarbonising_Shipping_2021.pdf

¹¹<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Glossary:Biofuels#:~:text=Liquid%20biofuels%20includes%20all%20liquid,liquid%20fuels%20from%20fossil%20origin>

(FAME)¹². The main differences between the two are the chemical compositions, performances in cold weather and storage qualities.

The Hydrotreated Vegetable Oil (HVO) estimated total world production of 2020 is at 6-7 million tons, while the existing production capacity in the EU stands at 12 million tons per year, the actual demand in various industries, in transport, requires additional infrastructure.

It is important to highlight that the production of HVO or FAME from biomass such as oil seeds could represent a barrier in its development considering the negative Indirect Land Use Change (ILUC) effects¹³, it is noted that advanced biofuels produced from feedstocks have lower life cycle emissions than fossil fuel. While both fuels produce similar amounts of carbon dioxide during combustion, liquid biofuels's carbon dioxide emissions are biogenic.

3.2.2 RENEWABLE GASEOUS FUELS

Compressed biogas (CBG) is viable for short-distance transport, such as small road vehicles and vessels travelling shorter distances, but not for deep-sea shipping due to its large storage volume and frequent refuelling requirements. Liquefied biogas (LBG) faces limitations in the shipping industry due to insufficient refuelling infrastructure. Currently, Sweden is one of the largest producers of LBG globally, with the Port of Gothenburg providing LBG bunkering (Offshore Energy, 2019). Moreover, ESL Shipping, based in Finland, introduced the first 100% renewable LBG dry bulk carrier to its fleet (Bioenergy Insight, 2020). However, CBG and LBG face supply chain issues due to the dispersed availability of organic feedstock and high transportation costs, making them less economically viable for shipping. Methanation offers higher scalability without biomass feedstock, but it is hindered by the need for CO₂ feedstock and low technological readiness. Consequently, CBG, LBG, and methanation have limited potential for international shipping, though they may be useful in specific maritime situations.

CBG is an alternative to Compressed Natural Gas (CNG), offering much lower greenhouse gas emissions and net-zero sulphur emissions. However, its energy density is much lower (7.2 GJ/m³) compared to MGO at 36.6 GJ/m³. With the shipping industry shifting from HFO to LNG, replacing LNG with LBG could further decarbonise the industry, reducing GHG emissions to near zero. LBG has an energy density of 21.2 GJ/m³, like liquefied methane at 23 GJ/m³, making both viable for long-distance shipping. Additionally, integrating bioenergy with BECCS can further reduce emissions from renewable gaseous fuels.

3.2.3 HYDROGEN

Currently, hydrogen (H₂) is primarily used for producing ammonia, especially in agriculture, accounting for 55% of its global usage. For hydrogen and ammonia to be used as fuels in the transport sector, particularly shipping, a significant increase in production is needed—potentially three times the current production to meet shipping fuel demands. Although H₂ has not yet been

¹² The terms HVO and FAME are used for renewable diesel fuels derived from hydrogenation and hydrocracking of different feedstocks such as tall oil, rapeseed oil, waste cooking oil and animal fats. It has similar chemical properties as fossil diesel, some differences are that it has a lower density and energy content than fossil diesel (Source: EU)

¹³ Indirect Land Use Change, which can occur when pasture or agricultural land previously destined for food and feed markets is diverted to biofuel production.

commercially used in shipping, plans are underway to use compressed and liquid H₂ in vessels. Shortly, H₂ will play a key role in shipping, mainly through indirect use to develop renewable fuels from green H₂. Direct use in hydrogen fuel cells and internal combustion engines will be more limited, with potential applications in short-distance shipping.

As reported in Table 3.1, currently, distribution and bunkering infrastructure for hydrogen doesn't exist and many regulatory and technical barriers need to be solved.

From the technical point of view: hydrogen is primarily produced using fossil fuels like coal and natural gas, with CCS helping to reduce emissions. However, for fully sustainable green H₂ production, water electrolysis powered by renewable energy is the ideal method. Unlike fossil fuel-based methods like Steam Methane Reforming (SMR) and Autothermal Reforming (ATR), electrolysis uses electricity to separate H₂ from water. Green H₂ is considered the best option for carbon-zero production. As a shipping fuel, H₂ can be stored as compressed gas, cryogenic liquid, or used to produce e-fuels like e-ammonia or e-methanol. However, H₂ storage is expensive and hazardous due to its flammability, requiring specially designed storage systems. Liquefied H₂ must be stored at -240°C and 13 bar pressure, which increases fuel tank weight and space requirements, reducing ship cargo capacity.

3.2.4 METHANOL

Global methanol production stands at 98 million tonnes (Mt) annually, generated by over 90 plants, with the industry contributing USD 55 billion in economic activity each year. Methanol is primarily used for formaldehyde synthesis, with other uses including olefin production, fuel blending, and DME production. As methanol use in shipping increases, according to Ming Leu et al., (2019), if methanol would be used to replace 50% of the world bunker demand, 328.9 Mt of global methanol production would be required, about triple of the current global production of methanol. This is a massive scale-up from current production levels, which would require about 22.6 million hectares of agricultural land equivalent to 0.46% of total global agricultural land use (Ming Liu, 2019). This would require major scaling of the methanol production industry to meet the demand for methanol across various sectors, including transport other than shipping.

Methanol benefits from established transportation and distribution infrastructure and does not require special storage for bunkering. However, one of the main issues with methanol scalability is the acquisition of cheap and renewable carbon sources to produce e-methanol. From a technical standpoint, e-methanol is a feasible fuel for the shipping sector due to the limited engine modifications required. However, there are challenges from an economic standpoint. From an operating expense perspective, the feedstock of renewable electricity is the main challenge, and from a capital expenditure perspective, the investment linked to the electrolysis itself is a challenge. Yet these latter factors represent a challenge for all renewable e-fuels. Particularly in the case of e-methanol, the key challenge is acquiring sustainable carbon capture, which is costly and adds to the final costs of e-methanol. Bio-methanol on the other hand relies on mature gasification technology but may be limited by the availability of biomass resources and the ability to scale up production via this thermochemical route. Despite these challenges, it is important to mention that key players in the shipping industry are devoting important resources to test the potential of renewable methanol via pilot projects (IRENA, 2021).

Methanol's storage temperature ranges from -93°C to 65°C , making it cheaper to store and transport than fuels like hydrogen, ammonia, and LNG. However, its lower energy density (15.8 GJ/m^3) is a concern compared to LNG (23.4 GJ/m^3) and MGO (36.6 GJ/m^3). This means methanol fuel tanks need to be about 2.5 times larger than those for MGO, reducing cargo space on ships. Despite this, methanol offers storage flexibility, as it does not require cryogenic conditions and can use existing tanks like slop or ballast tanks. Methanol also has a high energy efficiency rate of 70% during production. However, safety precautions are necessary due to the risk posed by its invisible flame when ignited, requiring additional fire detection, spill containment, and monitoring systems onboard ships.

3.2.5 AMMONIA

The global ammonia industry produces about 180 million tonnes (Mt) annually, with 80% used for agricultural fertiliser. China is the largest producer, primarily using coal, while the rest of the world relies on natural gas. Although there are currently no commercial applications of ammonia as a fuel in the shipping sector, significant interest and investment, particularly from South Korea, are focused on developing ammonia as a green shipping fuel. Ammonia has an advantage over other alternative fuels due to its existing transport and handling infrastructure, with established terminals worldwide, including Japan, the U.S., and Europe.

Renewable energy can be utilised to scale ammonia production globally, leveraging well-known methods like the Haber-Bosch process. Ports with ammonia bunkers could potentially produce their fuel using renewable energy sources. The industry is seeing momentum towards renewable ammonia, with projects aiming to produce 17 Mt annually by 2030—9% of current global production. Morocco, with its strategic location and renewable energy potential, could become a key bunkering hub. Other countries investing in renewable ammonia projects include Australia, Chile, Denmark, the Netherlands, and New Zealand, all utilising solar, wind, or mixed renewable energy sources.

Ammonia is a promising alternative shipping fuel due to its relatively easier and more affordable transportation and storage compared to hydrogen. It liquefies at -33°C , much higher than hydrogen's -253°C , and is nearly 50% more energy-dense per volume than liquid hydrogen, with a density of 12.7 GJ/m^3 . However, ammonia-fuelled ships would require 1.6 to 2.3 times more fuel volume compared to conventional heavy-fuel oil ships. Despite this, ammonia could reduce life-cycle greenhouse gas emissions by 83.7% to 92.1%. Ammonia-fuelled ships also need a pilot fuel, potentially hydrogen derived from onboard ammonia, to trigger combustion.

Using ammonia comes with safety challenges – such as low flammability, corrosion and toxicity – but an established infrastructure for handling and transporting ammonia exists and can apply the necessary safety measures (Kim et al., 2020). Indeed, ammonia has been handled in various applications for over a century and thus its hazardous nature and safe handling is considered a manageable challenge (Thorson Solvi and Ruhlman, 2020).

4 STAKEHOLDER DECARBONISATION STRATEGIES AND CHALLENGES

4.1 QUESTIONNAIRE STRUCTURE AND MAIN RESULTS

Within Task 2.2 activities, an online questionnaire, created using Microsoft Forms, has been distributed among project partners, COP and Advisory Boards Members. This questionnaire was designed to collect information and suggestions from key stakeholders regarding the technical, environmental, and regulatory aspects of the maritime sector's decarbonisation. A special emphasis was placed on the use of alternative fuels, such as biofuels, e-fuels, and e-methanol for vessel propulsion. The aim was to identify good practices, barriers, and the compatibility of stakeholder practices with the alternative fuel value chain.

53 stakeholders have answered the questionnaire, the following figure indicates the type of organisation they are part of, while Annex B reports the structure of the shared questionnaire. In particular, the graph in Figure 4.1 shows the participation of various stakeholders in the questionnaire: shipping companies had the highest number of respondents, indicating their significant involvement in the process; port operators and local authorities were also well represented, reflecting their critical role in developing the infrastructure for decarbonisation efforts; R&D project developers, ship engineering companies and logistics service providers were among the other key participants, underlining the wide interest throughout the maritime value chain. The presence of government agencies, fuel suppliers and educational institutions further highlights the diversity of actors involved in addressing the challenges of maritime decarbonisation.

Figure 4.1: Type of stakeholders involved

Around 49% of respondents say they are informed daily about issues related to the decarbonisation of the maritime sector and strategies to reduce emissions related to the shipping industry, whereas 46% of them report being quite familiar and occasionally updated. Finally, only 8% say they are not totally familiar with the issues related to the decarbonisation of the maritime sector and rarely stay informed.

Analysing the participation of stakeholders in projects and initiatives aimed at decarbonisation of the

maritime sector, it was found that about 26% of those interviewed are not involved in any initiative and 11% of the stakeholders surveyed plan to participate in initiatives and projects.

Several respondents indicated that they are not currently involved in the decarbonisation of the shipping sector due to their organisational roles or external constraints. Many explained that their companies do not own or manage fleets, but act as coordinators or users of transport services provided by carriers, placing the responsibility for decarbonisation on transport operators.

Some mentioned that they are guided by internal rules and policies, which do not currently make decarbonisation a priority, while others indicated that clearer guidelines at the state level would be needed to start involvement. Financial and technical challenges were also mentioned, with renewable fuels being costlier and more difficult to scale than fossil fuels.

Despite these challenges, the general attitude exists to consider decarbonisation in the future. Respondents were aware of possible new business opportunities and showed their readiness to participate once it fits within their role in the supply chain or when the external conditions allow for it. **Therefore, this indicates that the absence of engagement is not a question of lack of interest but rather more accessible practical solutions and an enabling regulatory environment.**

Regarding the initiatives currently ongoing, 23% of stakeholders interviewed lead initiatives and 40% participate actively in them. The activities currently conducted by the stakeholders are represented in Figure 4.2, where most of the current activities conducted by the 53 stakeholders are related to pilot projects (29%), energy management and operating optimisation (26%), on-shore power supply (18%) and fuel testing programmes (18%).

Figure 4.2: Breakdown of key activities carried out by stakeholders to support shipping decarbonization

Asking them about the barriers and challenges that they have faced in implementing activities and good practices, the responses reveal a diverse range of barriers to implementing decarbonisation practices across the maritime sector. These challenges can be grouped into financial, technological, regulatory, supply chain, and social factors, as follows:

Table 4.1: Main challenges faced in implementing decarbonisation activities

Type of Challenges	Description
Financial	One of the most frequently mentioned challenges is the high financial cost associated with adopting green technologies. These costs include investments in new fuels, onshore power supply and ship retrofiting. High costs in the EU area, combined with a lack of adequate financing mechanisms, make these transitions more difficult. In addition, high fuel prices and the need for private substations for electricity due to insufficient grid capacity impose additional financial burdens.
Technological	Several respondents identified the low level of technological maturity as a significant obstacle. Technologies such as electrolysis, large hydrogen storage to cope with variable renewable electricity supply, direct hydrogenation of CO ₂ and large-scale production of e-fuel are still in development. Many alternative fuels and propulsion methods are in their early stages of technological readiness (TRL), leading to uncertainties about performance, safety and integration. There is also a lack of standardised technologies, which makes players hesitant to invest. The maturity of marine applications is limited and new fuels such as ammonia and hydrogen require specialized safety and handling protocols.
Regulatory	The lack of clarity in the regulatory framework for decarbonisation is a significant obstacle. The strict regulatory standards for renewable fuels of non-biological origin (RFNBO) lead to higher production costs, making business cases difficult. Furthermore, the IMO's mandates for net zero greenhouse gas emissions are considered ambitious but lack the necessary policies and incentives to promote this change.
Supply Chain	Challenges related to fuel availability and infrastructure are often reported. The supply chain for alternative fuels is not yet fully developed, which means that there are logistical difficulties in bunkering new fuels. The green fuel distribution network, including charging stations for electric ferries, is incomplete and finding optimal locations for these facilities remains a challenge.
Social and Organizational	The responses highlight the cultural and skills challenges in the maritime sector. Shipowners and operators are opposed to change, driven by concerns about return on investment and reluctance to adopt new practices. There is also a shortage of skilled personnel to manage innovative fuels and technologies. The lack of a R&D culture in the sector further impedes progress, as there is little investment in research and testing for new solutions.

Figure 4.3: Main barriers and technical challenges in adopting alternative fuels for vessels

Figure 4.3 illustrates the main obstacles and technical challenges in the adoption of alternative fuels for ships, based on the stakeholders' survey responses. The main concerns are "Availability of alternative fuels" (20%) and "Cost of production of alternative fuel" (19%), highlighting challenges in terms of supply and economic feasibility. Compatibility of ship engines (18%) is another important issue, indicating the need for modifications or new technologies for the engines and Safety issues (12%) suggest compliance concerns and operational risks.

Other major obstacles include Infrastructure limitations (9%), Handling requirements (5%) and Production Sale (3%), highlighting gaps in support structures. Overall, the responses underline the need to improve fuel supply chains, reduce costs, ensure regulatory clarity and promote ship technology to facilitate the transition to alternative fuels.

When asked what technology is most promising to overcome the difficulties mentioned above, the replies point to several promising solutions for overcoming the challenges of adopting alternative fuels for ships. Methanol, hydrogen, ammonia and biofuels are considered key alternatives, with LNG engines and biofuels seen as transitional options. Electrification is feasible for smaller vessels where renewable energy is available. Infrastructure improvements, including large-scale fuel production, hydrogen networks and standardised bunkering protocols, are essential for scale-up adoption.

Technological advances such as AI, IoT and blockchain can improve emissions monitoring, route planning and regulatory compliance. Carbon capture, use and storage (CCUS) is promising but faces high costs and storage challenges. Energy optimisation of ships, including efficiency measures and improvements to machinery, can reduce emissions. Collaboration between governments, industry and technology developers is crucial to the successful development of solutions.

Many stakeholders believe the technology is ready, but a shift towards one or two alternative fuels is needed to rationalise supply chains. Regulatory and economic factors, such as reducing fossil fuel subsidies and encouraging green fuels, are also crucial. Ultimately, a combination of alternative fuels, infrastructure upgrading, digitisation and policy support is needed to achieve the

decarbonisation of maritime transport.

The key is the adoption and willingness of engine manufacturers to transform ship engines into those that can use alternative fuels. If engines are available, and therefore the shipowners require fuels, the high prices of alternative fuels will also decrease. In addition, to move the energy transition forward, the "world" needs first massive investment in renewable energy (solar, wind, hydroelectric) alternatively, nuclear power to produce green and pink electricity. This is fundamental and essential for adequate production of e-fuels. Adoption of alternative fuels by the shipping sector will be driven primarily by compliance with regulations coupled with financial (price) and operational (availability) considerations. Hybrid propulsion systems could play a pivotal role in the transition to alternative fuels, acting as a bridge between traditional fossil fuel dependence and the adoption of cleaner energy sources. By combining traditional fuels with biofuels, e-fuels, or electric propulsion, hybrid systems address several challenges in the energy transition.

Another important consideration (particularly for short-term measures) is the degree of alternative fuel compatibility with existing vessel engines (main propulsion and auxiliary generators) and fuel storage and supply systems. Existing regulations (FuelEU Maritime) require a modest penetration of alternative fuels - a carbon footprint of 77.94 gCO₂e/MJ is required for the fuel mixture in 2035 compared to 89.34 gCO₂e/MJ in 2025 (a drop of only 13% that can easily be achieved by efficiency measures and a very modest biofuel, eg. FAME or UCOME biodiesel, blending). On the other hand, between 2035 and 2050, a staggering drop of almost 75% in the carbon footprint is postulated. This will require the use of e-fuels or low-carbon biofuels, such as biomethanol, at significant levels which will put increasing pressure on onshore infrastructures (fuel production, storage and distribution) and will require significant investment in new buildings.

Regarding the safety and environmental impacts of alternative fuel use, 75% of the stakeholders who responded to the questionnaire say they have encountered (in practice or literature) safety or environmental risks. The main results described by the respondents, and confirmed by the literature described in the previous paragraphs, are shown in the following table:

Table 4.2: Main safety and environmental risks of using the main alternative fuels

Fuel Type	Safety Risks	Environmental Risks
Ammonia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Highly toxic: can cause severe respiratory damage, blindness and skin burns. • Corrosive: can damage ship's structures, pipelines and equipment. • Flammable under certain conditions: not highly flammable but may ignite in some scenarios. • Leakage hazards: even small leaks can be fatal in confined spaces. • Bunkering and handling risks: requires special management procedures and equipment. • Reactivity: may form explosive mixtures in certain environments. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Air pollution: the combustion of ammonia produces NO_x, which contributes to acid rain and smog. • Water contamination: ammonia spills can be lethal to marine life. • Chemical by-products: unburned ammonia emissions may contribute to environmental toxicity. • GHG emissions in use: produces nitrous oxide (NO), a powerful greenhouse gas. • Energy-intensive production: if produced using fossil fuels, ammonia's carbon footprint is still significant. • Water-intensive: Large-scale ammonia production requires significant freshwater

Fuel Type	Safety Risks	Environmental Risks
		resources.
Hydrogen	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extremely flammable and explosive: very low ignition energy, making it subject to accidental ignition. • Invisible flame: hydrogen fires are difficult to detect. • Storage risks: requires a cryogenic system or high-pressure storage, increasing the risk of leakage. • Risk of leakage: hydrogen molecules can escape easily, creating undetectable explosion risks. • Material degradation: Hydrogen fragility can weaken ship structures over time. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Production emissions: if derived from fossil fuels (grey hydrogen), its production emits a significant amount of CO₂, reducing its environmental benefits. • Energy-intensive production: requires a large amount of renewable electricity to be truly sustainable (green hydrogen). • Ocean warming potential: hydrogen released into water may alter the heat absorption properties of the oceans, although this effect is still being investigated. • Mining concerns: hydrogen fuel cells require platinum and rare earth metals, which have environmental and ethical sourcing issues.
E-Methanol	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➢ Highly flammable and volatile: has a low flash point (11 °C), which makes it subject to ignition. ➢ Toxic to humans: can cause blindness, neurological damage, or even death if inhaled, swallowed, or absorbed through the skin. ➢ Invisible flame hazard: methanol burns with a colourless flame, making it difficult to detect fire in daylight conditions. ➢ Risks of storage and handling: requires proper ventilation and specialized safety procedures to prevent exposure and combustion. ➢ Danger of leakage: can spread rapidly in confined spaces of the ship, resulting in a high risk of fire. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➢ Water solubility and marine toxicity: when poured, methanol dissolves in water and can damage marine life by disrupting ecosystems. ➢ Acidification of the oceans: Methanol spills can alter pH levels in water bodies, with consequences on biodiversity. ➢ Life-cycle emissions: if obtained from non-renewable sources, the environmental benefits of e-methanol are significantly reduced. ➢ Sustainability of production requires carbon capture or biomass for net zero emissions, which can be energy-intensive. ➢ Feedstock challenges: requires large-scale carbon capture or biomass feedstock.
Biofuels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➢ Explosions and fires: biofuels are fuels and require proper handling. ➢ Storage risks: can degrade over time, leading to fuel stability problems. ➢ Quality control problems: variability in fuel quality can cause engine performance risks. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➢ Deforestation and land use change: large-scale production of biofuels can contribute to the destruction of habitats. ➢ GHG emissions from production: cultivation, processing and transport can generate significant emissions. ➢ Water pollution: the runoff of fertilisers from biofuel crops can pollute watercourses.

Fuel Type	Safety Risks	Environmental Risks
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Competes with food supply: agricultural land used for biofuels could reduce global food availability.

Regarding regulatory aspects, the stakeholders affirm that the transition to alternative fuels in the maritime transport is significantly hampered by a **lack of global regulatory alignment** as different regions adopt different standards and policies, creating uncertainty for the industry (for long-time European regulations and IMO provisions were not aligned). In addition, **stringent safety requirements**, while essential for risk mitigation, often slow down the adoption of new technologies due to **slow approval processes for new fuels**. Financial barriers further complicate progress, as **limited financial incentives or subsidies** make alternative fuels less attractive to invest in. In addition, **fuel standards** inconsistent across jurisdictions create operational challenges, requiring ships to adapt to different regulations depending on where they operate. These problems are compounded by **complexities in policy implementation**, where overlapping and sometimes contradictory regulations make it difficult for shipping companies to navigate the transition effectively. For example, merchant shipping operates in a globalised international environment, which poses several obstacles to harmonised and efficient regulation, since it is necessary to reconcile competing national interests. For example, the EU has a very strict regulatory framework with sanctions in place but in a globalised sector, this can have negative implications as ships may try to avoid EU waters and move other activities outside of Europe.

Based on the responses to potential policy and incentive solutions, most respondents felt that a combination of regulatory changes and policy incentives would be appropriate, including:

- **carbon pricing mechanisms** such as the ETS, Carbon taxes and low-carbon fuel standards would make alternative fuels more competitive by increasing the cost of fossil fuels and encouraging a shift to greener options;
- **fuel mandates**, which could include blending requirements or standards based on life-cycle greenhouse gas intensity, would ensure a steady demand for sustainable fuels, pushing industry towards low-emission alternatives;
- **infrastructure investments**, essential to overcome logistical barriers, including the development of a global green bunkering network, port facilities for bunkering alternative fuels (such as hydrogen, ammonia or methanol) and power plants on the ground;
- **public-private partnerships and financial incentives**, such as subsidies for alternative fuels, tax incentives for ship modernisation or construction of new fuel-flexible ships, as well as grants for pilot projects, would further encourage the move to these cleaner technologies. These investments would reduce initial costs for shipping companies, facilitating the adoption of alternative fuels;
- **global harmonisation of regulations** would simplify the adoption of alternative fuels across all regions and minimise regulatory fragmentation. Aligning national regulations with international frameworks, such as the IMO decarbonisation strategy, and ensuring consistent infrastructure standards would facilitate global adoption. Efforts are also needed to reduce the gap between fossil fuel prices and new fuels through policy measures and financial incentives, to ensure that alternative fuels are more cost-competitive and accessible.

Based on the main highlights discussed above, each respondent was asked to highlight key actions that the maritime sector should prioritise to support the adoption of alternative fuels for decarbonisation. The responses have been organised and presented in the following figure:

Figure 4.4: Key actions to support the adoption of alternative fuels for decarbonization in the maritime sector

In the following section the main conclusion of the survey has been drafted, highlighting what decarbonization opportunities represent for different stakeholders and what their role is within the value chain of alternative fuels and e-methanol.

4.2 DECARBONISATION OBJECTIVES IMPACTS ON STAKEHOLDERS' ACTIVITIES

Based on the results of the questionnaire and the literature review of previous sections, this section will examine how key stages of the e-methanol value chain are affected by decarbonisation targets set for the maritime sector.

In Table 4.3, the key stakeholders, the challenges they face and the specific impacts on each of them are listed.

Table 4.3: Decarbonization objective impacts on Stakeholders' activities

Phase	Stakeholders involved	Barriers and constraints	Impact on Stakeholders
<p>Production of e-methanol</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Renewable energy providers; Electrolysis manufacturers, CO₂ providers and CO₂ capture technology developers. 	<p>The production of e-methanol is expensive due to the high costs of renewable energy inputs and CO₂ capture technologies. Additionally, scalability is limited by current infrastructure, and securing a stable CO₂ supply can be challenging.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Renewable energy suppliers will need to invest in expanding their capacity and ensure that energy supply is reliable and affordable for e-methanol production. CO₂ capture technology providers face the challenge of reducing costs and ensuring consistent CO₂ availability
<p>Logistic</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Logistics providers; Fuel transportation companies; Port operators. 	<p>Significant investment will be required in transportation infrastructure, including specialised vessels and storage tanks. Safety concerns related to fuel handling, especially during transportation, will require rigorous safety protocols and additional investments.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Port authorities will face the challenge of developing the necessary infrastructure for e-methanol bunkering terminals, including the construction of new storage facilities, bunkering systems, and safety equipment; Fuel transporters will need to manage the complexities of transporting e-methanol safely, requiring training for personnel and the development of secure logistics chains; Supply Chain Constraints: the shortage of tankers and land-based vehicles capable of carrying e-methanol could delay the deployment of the fuel at scale, leading to higher costs
<p>Storage and Handling in Ports</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Port authorities; Fuel suppliers; Regulatory bodies; Infrastructure developers. 	<p>Ports must deal with the high upfront costs of developing e-methanol storage facilities, including building storage tanks, and bunkering terminals, and ensuring safety and environmental compliance.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Port authorities will be required to invest in bunkering infrastructure to accommodate e-methanol. In addition, ports will need to work on standardizing bunkering procedures and safety protocols to handle this new fuel; Regulatory bodies will need to create and enforce regulations for e-methanol bunkering, focusing on safety, environmental standards, and operational procedures. Supply Chain Constraints: existing infrastructure may not be compatible with e-methanol, meaning retrofitting and significant

Phase	Stakeholders involved	Barriers and constraints	Impact on Stakeholders
 Use onboard	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shipowners; • Shipyards; • Engine manufacturers; • Fuel suppliers. 	<p>Retrofitting vessels is expensive and technically challenging. The costs and time required for retrofitting may deter many shipowners from adopting e-methanol.</p> <p>New builds are also costly, as they require specialised engines and fuel storage systems to accommodate alternative fuels.</p>	<p>capital investment may be required.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shipowners will face significant capital expenditures for retrofitting or building new vessels capable of using e-methanol. These costs may be further exacerbated by operational complexities and the need for crew retraining; • Engine manufacturers will be required to develop engines that are compatible with e-methanol, while also ensuring they meet international emission standards; • Supply Chain Constraints: the compatibility of vessels with e-methanol will depend on the availability of suitable retrofitting solutions and the readiness of fuel suppliers to deliver the required quantities at scale
 Regulatory and Policy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Government; • International organisations (IMO, EU, etc.); • Regulatory bodies. 	<p>Uncertainty around policy consistency and global cooperation may hinder investments in e-methanol. Countries with different regulatory environments could create fragmentation in the adoption of the fuel.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Governments will need to align their national decarbonisation strategies with international objectives, offering incentives for investments in e-methanol production and infrastructure; • International bodies will need to establish clear guidelines for alternative fuel adoption and coordinate efforts across different jurisdictions to avoid regulatory divergence. • Supply Chain Constraints: Lack of consistent global regulations and the challenge of developing infrastructure in certain regions could slow down the widespread adoption of e-methanol.

In addition, the role of ports is recognised in the Clydebank Declaration of the Conference of the Parties 26 (COP26), which pledges to establish green shipping corridors, i.e., routes that leverage collaboration across multiple stakeholders operating between two or more ports. The aim is to offer bunkering options for vessels running on low or zero-carbon fuels, test various solutions and support first movers in their efforts. Ports should not only offer bunkering options for low/zero carbon vessels but also run on zero-emissions equipment themselves to ensure truly green corridors. Since the signing of the Clydebank Declaration, 21 green shipping corridor initiatives have emerged (Global Maritime Forum, 2022). More than 110 stakeholders from across the value chain are engaged in these initiatives, with a high level of public–private collaboration.

Translating the green corridor concept into concrete action requires assessing the feasibility of such corridors. These corridors can help to reduce the costs of zero-emission fuels, enable the mobilisation of demand, and lower risks to incentivise stakeholder investment (McKinsey, 2022). Experiences with green shipping corridors will vary by region and will entail both challenges and opportunities. Most initiatives are still at an early stage and corridors currently considered are in the feasibility study phase (Global Maritime Forum, 2022). Going forward, it will be important to clarify whether the corridor projects will morph into a lasting solution once the demonstration phase is completed (Hubatova, 2022).

It will also be important to revisit the concept and ensure more inclusiveness in terms of vessel types, shipping routes and geographic distribution.

Stakeholders participating in green shipping corridors in Asia and the Pacific face various challenges, notably, a lack of awareness and insufficient infrastructure for green shipping such as green energy bunkering facilities or green energy plants. The study underscores the links between green shipping corridors and digitalisation. It demonstrates how digitalisation could further promote shipping decarbonisation, and enable seamless cargo, and ship traffic along the green shipping corridors.

4.3 STAKEHOLDER'S ROLE WITHIN THE VALUE CHAIN AIMING TO DECARBONISATION

In conclusion, decarbonisation solutions that mainly involve alternative fuels such as e-methanol, hydrogen and ammonia, according to stakeholders involved, represent huge opportunities combined with enormous challenges. While they are likely to transform into sustainable business models, maintain long-term environmental benefits and be aligned with global regulatory trends, significant upfront costs, major retrofit interventions and operational complexity are involved.

For **shipowners and operators, the switch to alternative fuels requires substantial investments in ship retrofitting, new equipment and crew training.** Lack of technological maturity, the energy-intensive process of fuel production, and the lack of renewable sources are adding further complications to such transitions. Issues such as storage capacity, safety risks, and energy efficiency are yet to be sorted out for large-scale use. Despite these challenges, the shipping industry recognises that such solutions are essential to achieving long-term sustainability objectives and reducing emissions.

Ports play a crucial role in the adoption of alternative fuels, including e-methanol, by **investing in infrastructure to support the safe handling, storage and distribution of these fuels.** As port authorities, their main role would be to ensure that the transition to alternative fuels can be carried out safely and effectively. To achieve this, the main tasks a port should undertake include the

development of bunker infrastructures, The establishment of new bunkering standards and work on building emergency response capacity to manage alternative fuel incidents. This would directly involve the costs for building storage facilities, and bunkers and installing essential safety equipment such as gas detectors, water tents and investments in drone monitoring capacity. In addition, training of on-board and ground personnel is critical and requires collaboration with industry experts, fuel testing and local training providers to ensure that courses are certified and meet industry standards.

The wider supply chain, involving **fuel producers, logistics companies and ship operators** will need to adjust to new dynamics that these alternative fuels bring to the table. In the specific case of e-methanol, the value chain starts with green methanol production from renewable resources, requiring investment in green hydrogen production, CO₂ capture technologies and renewable energy sources. This will require **close coordination among various stakeholders, including energy suppliers, shipping companies, and ports**, each acting to the tune of governmental policies. The shipping companies would look for reliable fuel suppliers that would meet their needs while meeting strict emission regulations, and port authorities and logistics providers must ensure adequate infrastructure for fuel storage and bunkering.

Although the cost of production of e-methanol remains high because of the energy-intensive nature of its production, it presents a promising solution for the decarbonisation of shipping. In the long term, to ensure sustainability for e-methanol as a valuable marine fuel, efforts need to be concentrated on **cost reduction in production, scaling up infrastructure, and a reliable supply chain right from production to end use**. Consequently, policies and incentives become important to reduce the risk associated with these investments and attract the scale of capital that widespread implementation would require.

Regulatory structures would be the sine qua non for such a shift. As believed by stakeholders, although decarbonisation solutions are expensive, the long-term values outweigh the financial burden in the short run. Policies that will and incentivise alternate fuels-for example, through grants or financial incentives-can offset investments and encourage the sector to go ahead.

Government, regulators, shipowners, fuel producers, and technology suppliers will need to work together with a view to minimizing risks and standardizing and simplifying the transition.

It means the pathway to decarbonisation, though quite essential, with key financial, technical, and operational challenges, has great recognition by the shipping industry of such a need for investment in sustainable technologies. With balancing such costs against long-term benefits like regulatory compliance, fuel efficiency, and emission reductions, comes the commitment from stakeholders for a transformation towards sustainability in the maritime sector.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The decarbonisation of the maritime transport sector presents both challenges and opportunities. Without further policy action, GHG emissions could increase by 16% by 2030 and 50% by 2050 (IMO, 2023). Achieving the Paris Agreement targets requires immediate reductions and achieving emission neutrality by 2040 or 2050, supported by strong new fuels, technologies and policies.

Given the international character of maritime transport, the principle of common but differentiated responsibilities shall be observed so as not to harm vulnerable economies. **Economic mechanisms**, such as taxes on greenhouse gas-emitting fuels, will give opportunities to invest in alternative fuels and finance decarbonisation, thus making it easier for developing nations to make the transition.

The **IMO's proposed medium-term measures** aim to generate funds to support this transition, including mitigation of economic impacts and improvement of port infrastructure (UNCTAD, 2023).

Alternative fuels such as e-methanol, hydrogen and ammonia offer promising decarbonisation routes but face significant financial, technical and regulatory barriers.

Among these, e-methanol stands out for its potential **compatibility with existing infrastructure** and its relatively lower complexity compared to hydrogen and ammonia. However, its wide-scale adoption requires overcoming key challenges, including **high production costs, the need for renewable energy sources and the development of efficient production processes**.

Shipowners and operators must make significant investments in modernising vessels, acquiring new equipment and training staff. The technological immaturity of these fuels, their energy-intensive production processes and the current lack of renewable energy sources complicate widespread adoption. In addition, safety risks, storage capacity and efficiency concerns remain unresolved.

Ports are key to the transition towards alternative fuels such as e-methanol, investing in storage, handling and distribution infrastructure. They must develop bunkering facilities, safety measures and training programmes to meet industry standards. The wider supply chain, including **fuel producers and shipping companies**, also needs to adapt, requiring investment in green hydrogen, CO₂ capture and renewable energy. Despite high costs, e-methanol remains a promising solution for decarbonisation, with policies and incentives needed to support its adoption. **Regulatory structures** will be crucial for risk management and the standardisation of procedures.

The success of e-methanol as a marine fuel depends on the collaboration of all stakeholders, from policymakers and investors to shipowners, ports and fuel producers. Although e-methanol is a viable route to decarbonisation due to its compatibility with existing infrastructure, significant investment and political support are needed to overcome economic and technical barriers. Stakeholders need to work together to increase production, improve supply chain logistics and establish clear regulatory frameworks. With coordinated efforts and the right incentives, electronic methanol has the potential to play a key role in the transition of the maritime sector towards a low-carbon future.

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ANNEX A - SHIP TYPE DEFINITION

The IMO study was conducted using generic vessel type estimate made available by GFW, where the vessels were classified into one of the six vessels groups: Fishing, Passenger, Cargo, Reefer, Tanker and Other. These correspond with the defined IMO vessel types:

- **Fishing:** miscellaneous - fishing;
- **Passenger:** Cruise, Ferry-ro pax, Ferry-pax only;
- **Cargo:** Bulk carrier, Container, General cargo, Ro-Ro, Vehicle carrier;
- **Reefer:** Refrigerated bulk;
- **Tanker:** Oil tanker, Chemical tanker, Liquefied gas tanker, Other liquid tanker;
- **Other:** Service-other, Service-tug, Offshore, Yacht, Miscellaneous - other.

While there are no universally applicable definitions of ship types, specific descriptions and names are used within IMO treaties and conventions. The following is a non-exhaustive list ship types defined in various IMO instruments¹⁴:

- A **passenger ship** is a ship which carries more than twelve passengers. (SOLAS I/2)
- A **fishing vessel** is a vessel used for catching fish, whales, seals, walrus or other living resources of the sea. (SOLAS I/2)
- **Fishing vessel** means any vessel used commercially for catching fish, whales, seals, walrus or other living resources of the sea. (SFV 1993 article 2)
- A **nuclear ship** is a ship provided with a nuclear power plant. (SOLAS I/2)
- **Bulk carrier** means a ship which is constructed generally with single deck, top-side tanks and hopper side tanks in cargo spaces, and is intended primarily to carry dry cargo in bulk, and includes such types as ore carriers and combination carriers. (SOLAS IX/1.6)
- **Bulk carrier** means a ship which is intended primarily to carry dry cargo in bulk, including such types as ore carriers and combination carriers. (SOLAS XII/1.1)
- **Oil tanker** means a ship constructed or adapted primarily to carry oil in bulk in its cargo spaces and includes combination carriers, any "NLS tanker" as defined in Annex II of the present Convention and any gas carrier as defined in regulation 3.20 of chapter II-1 of SOLAS 74 (as amended), when carrying a cargo or part cargo of oil in bulk. (MARPOL Annex I reg. 1.5)
- **General cargo ship:** A ship with a multi-deck or single-deck hull designed primarily for the carriage of general cargo. (MEPC.1/Circ.681 Annex)
- **High-speed craft** is a craft capable of travelling at high speed. (SOLAS X/1.2, HSC Code 2000 para 1.4.30)
- **Mobile offshore drilling unit (MODU)** means a vessel capable of engaging in drilling operations for the exploration for or exploitation of resources beneath the sea-bed such as liquid or gaseous hydrocarbons, sulphur or salt. (SOLAS IX/1, MODU Code 2009 para 1.3.40)

¹⁴ <https://www.imo.org/en/OurWork/Safety/Pages/RegulationsDefault.aspx>

- **Special purpose ship (SPS)** means a mechanically self-propelled ship which by reason of its function carries on board more than 12 special personnel. (SPS Code para 1.3.12).

In addition to the previous definitions provided by IMO, based on the “Implementation of Shipping MRV Regulation Determination of cargo carried”¹⁵, additional ship type definition are listed below:

- **Chemical tanker** is cargo ship constructed or adapted and used for the carriage of any liquid chemicals in bulk. (“Chemical tanker” or an “NLS tanker” as defined in MARPOL Annex II, regulation 1)
- **LNG carrier** is a tanker for the bulk carriage of Liquefied Natural Gas (primarily methane) in independent insulated tanks. Liquefaction is achieved at temperature down to -163°C.
- **Ro-pax ship** means a passenger ship with roll-on-roll-off cargo space
- **Container / Ro-Ro cargo ship** means a hybrid of a container ship and a ro-ro cargo ship in independent sections

¹⁵ https://climate.ec.europa.eu/document/download/fea9df17-9022-46c6-bab0-6e8406a08c10_en

ANNEX B - QUESTIONNAIRE STRUCTURE

The Questionnaire, distributed through Microsoft Forms, was structured as follows:

SECTION 1: GENERAL INFORMATION

- **Please provide your name**
.....
- **Please provide your organization name**
.....
- **Please provide your role in your organization**
.....
- **Please specify the type of Organization**
 - Shipping company
 - Ship builder (including engine manufacturers)
 - Port operator or local authority
 - Fuel or Technology provider (including CO₂, H₂ providers)
 - Government/Regulatory Body
 - R&D Project development
 - Other.....
- **What are the main activities of your organization?** *(Please provide a brief description of the main activity of your organization)*
.....
- **How familiar are you with maritime decarbonization and the strategies being implemented to reduce carbon emissions in the shipping industry?**
 - Very familiar, I stay informed daily
 - Quite familiar, I occasionally stay informed
 - Totally unfamiliar, I rarely stay informed.....
- **Are you or your organization currently involved in the decarbonization of maritime sector?**
 - Not involved
 - Planning to engage
 - Actively participating
 - Leading initiatives.....
- **If involved, specify your current activities** *(if applicable, select more than one)*
 - Pilot projects

- Fuel testing programs
- Energy management and operating optimization
- On-shore power supply
- Other

.....

- **If applicable, what have been the main barriers or challenges you have encountered in implementing these good practices (e.g. financial, technological, supply chain issues)?**

.....

- **If not involved, please explain the reason and if you expect to be involved in the future**

.....

SECTION 2: KEY INNOVATIVE CHALLENGES FOR ACCELERATING ALTERNATIVE FUEL ADOPTION

- **In your opinion, which are the main barriers and technical challenges in adopting alternative fuels for vessels? (if applicable, select more than one)**

- Infrastructure limitations
- Vessel engine compatibility
- Fuel availability
- Production sale
- Fuel storage conditions
- Handling requirements
- Production cost of the fuel
- Safety issues
- Other

.....

- **If applicable, please provide your personal and technical experience**

.....

- **Which technological solutions, in your view, are most promising for overcoming these challenges?**

.....

- **Is there a need for additional research or innovation in alternative fuel technologies? If so, in what areas (e.g. fuel production, engine optimization, supply chain improvements)?**

.....

- **What role do you see for hybrid propulsion systems in the transition to alternative fuels (e.g. combinations of traditional fuels with biofuels, e-fuels, or electric propulsion)?**

.....

- **Do you think there may be safety or environmental risks in the use of alternative fuels?**

- Yes
 - No
-

- If yes, please specify potential safety and environmental concerns do you foresee with the use of alternative fuels (e.g., ammonia, hydrogen, e-methanol) in vessels? Please provide specific examples if possible.
-
- In your opinion, what are the main negative environmental impacts or risks associated with the production and use of alternative fuels in shipping?
-

SECTION 3: REGULATORY ASPECTS FOR ALTERNATIVE FUEL ADOPTION

- Have you faced or identified any regulatory barriers hindering the use of alternative fuels in the maritime sector (e.g. lack of global regulatory alignment, stringent safety requirements, slow approval process for new fuels, limited financial incentives or subsidies)?
 - Yes
 - No
-
- If applicable, please share your experience and your opinion
-
- Which changes in regulation or policy would significantly accelerate the decarbonization of maritime shipping through alternative fuels? (e.g. carbon pricing mechanisms, fuel mandates, tax incentives, infrastructure investment)
-
- If applicable, how does your organization ensure compliance with existing environmental regulations related to decarbonization? *Please describe the measures and practices to adhere to relevant standards and regulations. For instance, how do you monitor emissions or utilize low-sulfur fuels in shipping to comply with IMO regulations or adopt carbon capture technologies in industrial processes to meet local emissions standards. Additionally, details on any emissions reporting systems or regulatory frameworks you follow would be helpful.*

SECTION 4: OUTLOOK AND RECOMMENDATIONS

- In your view, what are the next most important steps the maritime sector must take to advance the use of e-methanol and other e-fuels for decarbonization?
 - Investment in fuel production capacity
 - Fleet conversion programs
 - R&D project implementation
 - Policy reforms
 - Infrastructure implementation
 - Other
-
- How familiar are you with the topics and the technologies mentioned in this questionnaire, such as carbon capture and alternative fuels?
 - Very familiar
 - Quite familiar

Totally unfamiliar

-
- **What do these technologies and the decarbonization solutions represent for you in terms of costs, retrofitting requirements, and their potential impacts?**
-
- **If you want, please share any additional key points you believe will be critical to consider in the value chain for the production and use of alternative fuels in the maritime sector.**